

برنامه کامل

پروژه تبدیل اطلاعات اصطلاحنامه از یک فایل متنی به ساختار اطلاعاتی نرم افزار ساخت اصطلاحنامه "قاموس"

طراحی و اجرا: مهرداد نوروزی اقبالی

بِسْمِ اللَّهِ الرَّحْمَنِ الرَّحِيمِ

```
//-----  
#include <vcl.h>  
#pragma hdrstop  
//-----  
USEFORM("Process.cpp", Form1);  
//-----  
WINAPI WinMain(HINSTANCE, HINSTANCE, LPSTR, int)  
{  
    try  
    {  
        Application->Initialize();  
        Application->CreateForm(__classid(TForm1), &Form1);  
        Application->Run();  
    }  
    catch (Exception &exception)  
    {  
        Application->ShowException(&exception);  
    }  
    catch (...)  
    {  
        try  
        {  
            throw Exception("");  
        }  
        catch (Exception &exception)  
        {  
            Application->ShowException(&exception);  
        }  
    }  
    return 0;  
}  
//-----
```

```

#include <vcl.h>
#include <ComCtrls.hpp>
#include <odbcinst.h>

#include "Functions.hpp"
#include "Unicode.hpp"

enum RV {
    RV_OK,                // Okay, Success, True, whatever

    // -- Usage and environment errors --
    RV_USAGE,             // Invalid command line
    RV_NOT_ENOUGH_SPACE,  // Not enough space for backup
    RV_FILE_LOCKED,       // DB was locked by another process
    RV_OPEN_FILE,         // Invalid filename or could not open
    RV_CHANGE_DIRECTORY,  // Error chdiring to the location of the mdb
    RV_WORKING_DIR,       // Error chdiring to the specified working dir

    // -- Errors from SQLConfigDataSource() --
    RV_DB_COMPACTION,     // Database compaction failed
    RV_CREATE_DB,         // Failed to create DB
    RV_REPAIR_DB,         // Failed to repair DB
    RV_CREATE_DSN,        // Failed to create DSN

    // -- Technical errors --
    RV_GET_FILE_SIZE,     // Error getting file size
    RV_GET_DISK_SPACE,    // Error getting disk space
    RV_MOVE_FILE,         // Could not move database
    RV_MAKE_BACKUP_COPY,  // Could not create a backup copy
    RV_NO_SAFE_PATHNAME,  // Could not get a shortened form of a pathname
    RV_RESTORE_FILE,     // Could not move database back to original location when done

    RV_MAX
};

int __fastcall CreateAccessDatabase(char *FileName)
{
    AnsiString Attributes;
    char *Pos;
    char *Driver = "Microsoft Access Driver (*.mdb)";

    Attributes = Format("CREATE_DB=\"%s\" General;;", ARRAYOFCONST(((char *)FileName)));
    Pos = Attributes.c_str();

    do
    {
        if(*Pos == ';')
            *Pos = 0;
        Pos++;
    }while(*Pos);

    return SQLConfigDataSource(NULL, ODBC_CONFIG_SYS_DSN, Driver, Attributes.c_str());
}

```

```

//-----
bool IsDigitalString(const wchar_t *String)
{
    for(unsigned register i = 0; i < wcslen(String); i++)
        if(!iswdigit(String[i]))
            return false;

    return true;
}
//-----

int ThesaurusSpecialCompare(WideString s1, WideString s2, unsigned len)
{
    int ReturnValue;

    if(IsDigitalString(s1) && IsDigitalString(s2) && !s1.IsEmpty() && !s2.IsEmpty())
        ReturnValue = StrToInt(s1) - StrToInt(s2);
    else
    {
        AnsiString Str1 = s1;
        AnsiString Str2 = s2;

        if(
            (*Str1.c_str() == '[' && *Str1.AnsiLastChar() == ']') ||
            (*Str1.c_str() == ']' && *Str1.AnsiLastChar() == '[')
        )
        {
            Str1.Delete(1, 1);
            Str1.Delete(Str1.Length(), 1);
        }

        if(
            (*Str2.c_str() == '[' && *Str2.AnsiLastChar() == ']') ||
            (*Str2.c_str() == ']' && *Str2.AnsiLastChar() == '[')
        )
        {
            Str2.Delete(1, 1);
            Str2.Delete(Str2.Length(), 1);
        }

        ReturnValue = Str1.AnsiCompareIC(Str2);
    }

    return ReturnValue;
}
//-----

int AnsiStringCompare(WideString s1, WideString s2, unsigned len)
{
    return WideCompareStr(s1, s2);
}
//-----

```

```
int AnsiStringCompareIC(WideString s1, WideString s2, unsigned len)
{
    return WideCompareText(s1, s2);
}
//-----

void RemoveSpace(AnsiString *String)
{
    char ch = *String->c_str();

    while(ch == ' ' || ch == '\t' || ch == '\r' || ch == '\n')
    {
        String->Delete(1, 1);
        ch = *String->c_str();
    }

    if(!String->IsEmpty())
    {
        ch = *String->AnsiLastChar();
        while(ch == ' ' || ch == '\t' || ch == '\r' || ch == '\n')
        {
            String->SetLength(String->Length() - 1);
            if(!String->IsEmpty())
                ch = *String->AnsiLastChar();
        }
    }
}
//-----

void RemoveSpace(WideString *String)
{
    if(!String->IsEmpty())
    {
        wchar_t ch = *String->c_bstr();
        int Len;

        if(!ch)
            String->Empty();
        else
        {
            while(ch == ' ' || ch == '\t' || ch == '\r' || ch == '\n')
            {
                String->Delete(1, 1);
                if(!String->IsEmpty())
                    ch = *String->c_bstr();
                else
                    break;
            }

            if(!String->IsEmpty())
            {
                Len = String->Length();
            }
        }
    }
}
```

```
        ch = String->c_bstr()[Len - 1];
        while(ch == ' ' || ch == '\t' || ch == '\r' || ch == '\n')
        {
            String->SetLength(--Len);
            if(!String->IsEmpty())
                ch = String->c_bstr()[Len - 1];
        }
    }
}
```

```
//-----
void RemoveSpace(char *Str)
```

```
{
    if(Str)
    {
        AnsiString String = Str;
        RemoveSpace(&String);
        StrCopy(Str, String.c_str());
    }
}
```

```
//-----
void RemoveSpace(wchar_t *Str)
```

```
{
    if(Str)
    {
        WideString String(Str);
        RemoveSpace((WideString *)&String);
        if(!String.IsEmpty())
            wcsncpy(Str, String);
        else
            *Str = 0;
    }
}
```

```
//-----
int SearchTreeView(TTreeView *TreeView, AnsiString *String)
```

```
{
    int ReturnValue = -1;

    for(register i = 0; i < TreeView->Items->Count; i++)
        if(!String->AnsiCompareIC(TreeView->Items->Item[i]->Text))
        {
            ReturnValue = i;
            break;
        }

    return ReturnValue;
}
```

```
//-----
```

```
int SearchTreeView(TTreeView *TreeView, WideString String)
{
    int ReturnValue = -1;
    AnsiString Str;

    for(register i = 0; i < TreeView->Items->Count; i++)
    {
        Str = TreeView->Items->Item[i]->Text;
        if(!StrICompW(String, (WideString)Str))
        {
            ReturnValue = i;
            break;
        }
    }

    return ReturnValue;
}
//-----
```

```
int SearchStringList(TStringList *List, AnsiString *String)
{
    int ReturnValue = -1;

    for(register i = 0; i < List->Count; i++)
        if(!String->AnsiCompareIC(List->Strings[i]))
        {
            ReturnValue = i;
            break;
        }

    return ReturnValue;
}
//-----
```

```
int SearchStringList(TWideStringList *List, WideString String)
{
    int ReturnValue = -1;

    for(register i = 0; i < List->Count; i++)
        if(!StrICompW(String, List->Strings[i]))
        {
            ReturnValue = i;
            break;
        }

    return ReturnValue;
}
//-----
```

```
int SearchStrings(TStrings *List, AnsiString *String)
{
    int ReturnValue = -1;
```

```
    for(register i = 0; i < List->Count; i++)
        if(!String->AnsiCompareIC(List->Strings[i]))
        {
            ReturnValue = i;
            break;
        }

    return ReturnValue;
}
//-----

int SearchStrings(TWideStrings *List, WideString *String)
{
    int ReturnValue = -1;

    for(register i = 0; i < List->Count; i++)
        if(!AnsiStringCompareIC(*String, List->Strings[i]))
        {
            ReturnValue = i;
            break;
        }

    return ReturnValue;
}
//-----

void RemoveDuplicateSpaces(AnsiString *Str)
{
    int Pos;

    while((Pos = Str->AnsiPos(" ")) > 0)
        Str->Delete(Pos, 1);
}
//-----

void RemoveDuplicateSpaces(char *Str)
{
    AnsiString String = Str;
    RemoveDuplicateSpaces(&String);
    StrCopy(Str, String.c_str());
}
//-----

void RemoveDuplicateSpaces(wchar_t *Str)
{
    if(Str)
    {
        int Pos;

        WideString String(Str);

        while((Pos = String.Pos(" ")) > 0)
            String.Delete(Pos, 1);
    }
}
```

```
        if(!String.IsEmpty())
            wcsncpy(Str, String);
        else
            *Str = 0;
    }
}
//-----

void Sort(TStringList *List, bool RemoveDuplicates, bool RemoveEmptyLines, bool RemoveAdditionalSpaces)
{
    int Pos;
    AnsiString Str;

    if(RemoveAdditionalSpaces)
    {
        for(register i = 0; i < List->Count; i++)
        {
            Str = List->Strings[i];
            RemoveSpace(&Str);
            RemoveDuplicateSpaces(&Str);
            List->Strings[i] = Str;
        }
    }

    List->Sort();

    if(RemoveDuplicates || RemoveEmptyLines)
        for(register i = 0; i < List->Count; i++)
        {
            if(RemoveDuplicates && i)
            {
                if(!List->Strings[i].AnsiCompareIC(List->Strings[i - 1]))
                {
                    List->Delete(i);
                    i--;
                }
            }
            else
                if(RemoveEmptyLines)
                {
                    if(List->Strings[i].IsEmpty())
                    {
                        List->Delete(i);
                        i--;
                    }
                }
        }
    }
}
//-----

void Sort(AnsiString *String, bool RemoveDuplicates, bool RemoveEmptyLines, bool RemoveAdditionalSpaces)
{

```

```

TStringList *List = new TStringList;
int Pos;

List->Text = *String;
Sort(List, RemoveDuplicates, RemoveEmptyLines, RemoveAdditionalSpaces);
*String = List->Text;

delete List;
}
//-----

```

```

void Sort(TWideStringList *List, bool RemoveDuplicates, bool RemoveEmptyLines, bool RemoveAdditionalSpaces)
{

```

```

    int Pos;
    WideString Str;

```

```

    if(RemoveAdditionalSpaces)
    {

```

```

        for(register i = 0; i < List->Count; i++)
        {

```

```

            Str = List->Strings[i];
            RemoveSpace(Str);
            RemoveDuplicateSpaces(Str);
            List->Strings[i] = Str;
        }
    }

```

```

    List->Sort();

```

```

    if(RemoveDuplicates || RemoveEmptyLines)
    for(register i = 0; i < List->Count; i++)
    {

```

```

        if(RemoveDuplicates && i)
        {

```

```

            if(CompareStringW(LOCALE_SYSTEM_DEFAULT, NORM_IGNORECASE,
                List->Strings[i], -1, List->Strings[i - 1], -1) == 2)
            {

```

```

                List->Delete(i);
                i--;
            }
        }
    }

```

```

    else

```

```

        if(RemoveEmptyLines)
        {

```

```

            if(List->Strings[i].IsEmpty())
            {

```

```

                List->Delete(i);
                i--;
            }
        }
    }
}
//-----

```

```
void Sort(WideString *String, bool RemoveDuplicates, bool RemoveEmptyLines, bool RemoveAdditionalSpaces)
{
    TWideStringList *List = new TWideStringList;
    int Pos;

    List->Text = *String;
    Sort(List, RemoveDuplicates, RemoveEmptyLines, RemoveAdditionalSpaces);
    *String = List->Text;

    if(List->Count < 2)
    {
        RemoveSpace((WideString *)String);
        RemoveDuplicateSpaces(*String);
    }

    delete List;
}
//-----

int __fastcall StringToInt(AnsiString Str)
{
    int ReturnValue = 0;
    if(!Str.IsEmpty())
        ReturnValue = StrToInt(Str);

    return ReturnValue;
}
//-----

bool __fastcall IsInNumericRange(AnsiString LowValueStr, AnsiString HiValueStr, int CurrentValue)
{
    bool ReturnValue = false;
    int Low, High;
    int Swap;

    Low = StringToInt(LowValueStr);
    High = StringToInt(HiValueStr);

    if(High < Low && !HiValueStr.IsEmpty() && !LowValueStr.IsEmpty())
    {
        Swap = High;
        High = Low;
        Low = Swap;
    }

    if((CurrentValue <= High || HiValueStr.IsEmpty()) &&
        (CurrentValue >= Low || LowValueStr.IsEmpty()))
        ReturnValue = true;

    return ReturnValue;
}
//-----
```

```
char * __fastcall AnsiStrPosIC(char * Str, char * SubStr)
{
    char *Str2 = new char[StrLen(Str) + 1], *SubStr2 = new char[StrLen(SubStr) + 1];
    char *Pos;
    char *ReturnValue = NULL;

    StrCopy(Str2, Str);
    StrCopy(SubStr2, SubStr);

    StrUpper(Str2);
    StrUpper(SubStr2);

    Pos = AnsiStrPos(Str2, SubStr2);

    if(Pos)
        ReturnValue = Str + int(Pos) - int(Str2);

    delete[] SubStr2;
    delete[] Str2;

    return ReturnValue;
}
//-----
```

```
wchar_t * __fastcall AnsiStrPosICW(wchar_t * Str, wchar_t * SubStr)
{
    WideString Str2(Str), SubStr2(SubStr);
    int Pos;
    wchar_t *ReturnValue = NULL;

    Str2 = Sysutils::WideUpperCase(Str2);
    SubStr2 = Sysutils::WideUpperCase(SubStr2);

    Pos = Str2.Pos(SubStr2);

    if(Pos)
        ReturnValue = Str + Pos - 1;

    return ReturnValue;
}
//-----
```

```
WideString WideCopy(WideString *dest, WideString *src, int Len)
{
    if(Len < 0)
        Len = src->Length();

    dest->Empty();
    if(Len)
        dest->Insert(*src, 0);
    dest->SetLength(Len);
}
```

```
    return *dest;
}
//-----

WideString WideCopy(WideString *dest, AnsiString src, int Len)
{
    if(Len < 0)
        Len = src.Length();

    dest->Empty();
    if(Len)
        dest->Insert(src, 0);
    dest->SetLength(Len);

    return *dest;
}
//-----

WideString WideCopy(WideString *dest, wchar_t *src, int Len)
{
    WideString Source(src, Len < 0 ? wcslen(src) : Len + 1);
    if(Len < 0)
        Len = Source.Length();

    dest->Empty();
    if(Len)
        dest->Insert(Source, 0);
    dest->SetLength(Len);

    return *dest;
}
//-----

int __fastcall WriteUnicode(TStream *Stream, wchar_t *Buffer, int Count)
{
    AnsiString String = "";
    wchar_t *Pos = Buffer;
    int Number;
    char ch[2] = " ";

    for(int i = 0; i < Count; ++i)
    {
        Number = (short unsigned)*Pos;

        if(Number < 128 && Number != L{' ' && Number != L{'})
        {
            ch[0] = Number;
            String += ch;
        }
        else
            String += "\\u" + IntToStr(Number) + " ";
        ++Pos;
    }
}
```

```
    return Stream->Write(String.c_str(), String.Length());  
}  
//-----
```

```
#include <ComCtrls.hpp>
#include <Unicode.hpp>
```

```
int AnsiStringCompare(WideString s1, WideString s2, unsigned len = 0);
int AnsiStringCompareIC(WideString s1, WideString s2, unsigned len = 0);
char * __fastcall AnsiStrPosIC(char * Str, char * SubStr);
wchar_t * __fastcall AnsiStrPosICW(wchar_t * Str, wchar_t * SubStr);
int __fastcall CreateAccessDatabase(char *FileName);
bool IsDigitalString(const char *String);
bool IsDigitalString(const wchar_t *String);
bool __fastcall IsInNumericRange(AnsiString LowValueStr, AnsiString HiValueStr, int CurrentValue);
void RemoveDuplicateSpaces(AnsiString *Str);
void RemoveDuplicateSpaces(char *Str);
void RemoveDuplicateSpaces(wchar_t *Str);
void RemoveSpace(WideString *String);
void RemoveSpace(AnsiString *String);
void RemoveSpace(char *str);
void RemoveSpace(wchar_t *Str);
int SearchStringList(TStringList *List, AnsiString *String);
int SearchStringList(TWideStringList *List, WideString String);
int SearchStrings(TStrings *List, AnsiString *String);
int SearchStrings(TWideStrings *List, WideString *String);
int SearchTreeView(TTreeView *TreeView, AnsiString *String);
int SearchTreeView(TTreeView *TreeView, WideString String);
void Sort(AnsiString *String, bool RemoveDuplicates = true, bool RemoveEmptyLines = true, bool RemoveDuplicateSpaces = true);
void Sort(TStringList *List, bool RemoveDuplicates = true, bool RemoveEmptyLines = true, bool RemoveDuplicateSpaces = true);
void Sort(WideString *String, bool RemoveDuplicates = true, bool RemoveEmptyLines = true, bool RemoveDuplicateSpaces = true);
void Sort(TWideStringList *List, bool RemoveDuplicates = true, bool RemoveEmptyLines = true, bool RemoveDuplicateSpaces = true);
int __fastcall StringToInt(AnsiString Str);
int ThesaurusSpecialCompare(WideString s1, WideString s2, unsigned len = 0);
WideString WideCopy(WideString *dest, WideString *src, int Len = -1);
WideString WideCopy(WideString *dest, AnsiString src, int Len = -1);
WideString WideCopy(WideString *dest, wchar_t *src, int Len = -1);
int __fastcall WriteUnicode(TStream *Stream, wchar_t *Buffer, int Count);
```

```
//-----  
#include <vcl.h>  
#pragma hdrstop  
  
#include "Process.h"  
#include "Functions.hpp"  
#include "WFbtree.h"  
//-----  
#pragma package(smart_init)  
#pragma link "TntStdCtrls"  
#pragma resource "*.dfm"  
TForm1 *Form1;  
//-----  
__fastcall TForm1::TForm1(TComponent* Owner)  
    : TForm(Owner)  
{  
}  
//-----  
  
void __fastcall TForm1::Button1Click(TObject *Sender)  
{  
    if(OpenDialog1->Execute())  
    {  
        LabeledEdit1->Text = OpenDialog1->FileName;  
    }  
}  
//-----  
  
void __fastcall TForm1::Button2Click(TObject *Sender)  
{  
    if(SaveDialog1->Execute())  
    {  
        LabeledEdit2->Text = SaveDialog1->FileName;  
    }  
}  
//-----  
  
void __fastcall TForm1::Button3Click(TObject *Sender)  
{  
    try  
    {  
        LoopEncountered = false;  
        if(!LabeledEdit2->Text.IsEmpty())  
        {  
            Form1->Enabled = false;  
  
            DeleteFile("~001data.tmp");  
            DeleteFile("~002data.tmp");  
            Tree = new Fbtree("~001data.tmp");  
            Linear = new Fbtree("~002data.tmp");  
  
            StatusBar1->SimpleText = "ساخت ایندکس...";  
        }  
    }  
}
```

```

FindAllTerms();
StatusBar1->SimpleText = "بهينه سازي..." ;
Linear->Optimize();

StatusBar1->SimpleText = "جستجوي واژه هاي ريشه..." ;
FindTopTerms();
StatusBar1->SimpleText = "بهينه سازي..." ;
Tree->Optimize();

Tree->Go(TOP);
StatusBar1->SimpleText = "ايجاد ساختار..." ;
MakeThesaurusStructure();

if(!LoopEncountered)
{
    StatusBar1->SimpleText = "لطفا صبر كنيد MS-Access. ذخيره با فرمت اطلاعاتي..." ;
    SendToMicrosoftAccess();
}

delete Linear;
delete Tree;

DeleteFile("~001data.tmp");
DeleteFile("~002data.tmp");
}
}
finally
{
    StatusBar1->SimpleText = "";
    Form1->Enabled = true;
    /*Button1->Enabled = true;
    Button2->Enabled = true;
    Button3->Enabled = true;*/
}
}
//-----

void __fastcall TForm1::FindAllTerms(void)
{
    if(!LabeledEdit1->Text.IsEmpty() && FileExists(LabeledEdit1->Text))
    {
        Record Rec;
        InputLines = new TWideStringList();

        InputLines->LoadFromFile(LabeledEdit1->Text);

        CountLines = 0;
        while(FindTextRecord(&Rec, CountLines))
        {
            SaveRecord(Linear, &Rec);
        }

        delete InputLines;
    }
}

```

```
    }
}
//-----

void __fastcall TForm1::FindTopTerms(void)
{
    if(!LabeledEdit1->Text.IsEmpty() && FileExists(LabeledEdit1->Text))
    {
        Record Rec;
        InputLines = new TWideStringList();

        InputLines->LoadFromFile(LabeledEdit1->Text);

        CountLines = 0;
        while(FindTextRecord(&Rec, CountLines, true))
        {
            if(Rec.USE.IsEmpty())
                SaveRecord(Tree, &Rec);
        }

        delete InputLines;
    }
}
//-----

bool __fastcall TForm1::FindTextRecord(Record *Rec, int LineNumber, bool OnlyTopTerms)
{
    int Counter = LineNumber, EndOfRecord;
    bool Done = false;
    bool ReturnValue = false;
    WideString String;
    int BTCounter;
    ThesaurusFields LastField;

    while(!Done && Counter < InputLines->Count)
    {
        ResetRecord(Rec);
        BTCounter = 0;

        Counter = CountLines = FindStartOfNextTextRecord(Counter - 1, OnlyTopTerms);
        EndOfRecord = FindStartOfNextTextRecord(Counter + 1);

        if(Counter < InputLines->Count)
        {
            String = InputLines->Strings[Counter++];

            LastField = MT;
            Rec->MT.Empty();
            if(RadioButton7->Checked)
            {
                if(Counter < InputLines->Count)
                {
                    Rec->MT = String;
                }
            }
        }
    }
}
//-----
```

```
        ReturnValue = true;
    }
}
else if(RadioButton6->Checked)
{
    if(Counter < InputLines->Count - 1)
    {
        Rec->MT = InputLines->Strings[Counter++];
        ReturnValue = true;
    }
}
else if(RadioButton5->Checked)
{
    if(Counter < InputLines->Count)
    {
        Rec->MT = String.SubString(TntEdit15->Text.Length() + 1, String.Length());
        ReturnValue = true;
    }
}

for(int i = Counter; i < EndOfRecord; ++i)
{
    String = InputLines->Strings[Counter++];
    RemoveSpace((WideString *)&String);

    if(!IsIgnorableLine(String))
    {
        if(CheckBox1->Checked && IsStartedWith(String, TntEdit1->Text))//BT
        {
            ADDWITHSEPARATOR(Rec->BT, String.SubString(TntEdit1->Text.Length() + 1, String.Length()));
            ++BTCounter;
            LastField = BT;
        }
        else if(CheckBox2->Checked && IsStartedWith(String, TntEdit2->Text))//NT
        {
            ADDWITHSEPARATOR(Rec->NT, String.SubString(TntEdit2->Text.Length() + 1, String.Length()))
            LastField = NT;
        }
        else if(CheckBox3->Checked && IsStartedWith(String, TntEdit3->Text))//RT
        {
            ADDWITHSEPARATOR(Rec->RT, String.SubString(TntEdit3->Text.Length() + 1, String.Length()))
            LastField = RT;
        }
        else if(CheckBox4->Checked && IsStartedWith(String, TntEdit4->Text))//USE
        {
            ADDWITHSEPARATOR(Rec->USE, String.SubString(TntEdit4->Text.Length() + 1, String.Length()))
            LastField = USE;
        }
        else if(CheckBox5->Checked && IsStartedWith(String, TntEdit5->Text))//UF
        {
            ADDWITHSEPARATOR(Rec->UF, String.SubString(TntEdit5->Text.Length() + 1, String.Length()))
            LastField = UF;
        }
    }
}
```

```
else if(CheckBox6->Checked && IsStartedWith(String, TntEdit6->Text))//SN
{
    Rec->SN += String.SubString(TntEdit6->Text.Length() + 1, String.Length());
    LastField = SN;
}
else if(CheckBox7->Checked && IsStartedWith(String, TntEdit7->Text))//HN
{
    Rec->HN += String.SubString(TntEdit7->Text.Length() + 1, String.Length());
    LastField = HN;
}
else if(CheckBox8->Checked && IsStartedWith(String, TntEdit8->Text))//IND
{
    Rec->IND += String.SubString(TntEdit8->Text.Length() + 1, String.Length());
    LastField = IND;
}
else if(CheckBox9->Checked && IsStartedWith(String, TntEdit9->Text))//Frq
{
    Rec->Frq += String.SubString(TntEdit9->Text.Length() + 1, String.Length());
    LastField = Frq;
}
else if(CheckBox10->Checked && IsStartedWith(String, TntEdit10->Text))//SC
{
    Rec->SC += " " + String.SubString(TntEdit10->Text.Length() + 1, String.Length());
    LastField = SC;
}
else if(CheckBox11->Checked && IsStartedWith(String, TntEdit11->Text))//Translate 1
{
    Rec->T1 += String.SubString(TntEdit11->Text.Length() + 1, String.Length());
    LastField = T1;
}
else if(CheckBox12->Checked && IsStartedWith(String, TntEdit12->Text))//Translate 2
{
    Rec->T2 += String.SubString(TntEdit12->Text.Length() + 1, String.Length());
    LastField = T2;
}
else if(CheckBox13->Checked && IsStartedWith(String, TntEdit13->Text))//Translate 3
{
    Rec->T3 += String.SubString(TntEdit13->Text.Length() + 1, String.Length());
    LastField = T3;
}
else
{
    if(CheckBox1->Checked && LastField == BT)//BT
    {
        ADDWITHSEPARATOR(Rec->BT, String);
        ++BTCounter;
    }
    else if(CheckBox2->Checked && LastField == NT)//NT
        ADDWITHSEPARATOR(Rec->NT, String)
    else if(CheckBox3->Checked && LastField == RT)//RT
        ADDWITHSEPARATOR(Rec->RT, String)
    else if(CheckBox4->Checked && LastField == USE)//USE
        ADDWITHSEPARATOR(Rec->USE, String)
```

```

        else if(CheckBox5->Checked && LastField == UF)//UF
            ADDWITHSEPARATOR(Rec->UF, String)
        else if(CheckBox10->Checked && LastField == SC)//SC
            Rec->SC += " " + String;
    }
}

if((OnlyTopTerms && !BTCounter) || !OnlyTopTerms || Counter >= InputLines->Count)
    Done = true;
}
else
    Done = true;
}

CountLines = Counter - 1;

return ReturnValue;
}
//-----

```

```

int __fastcall TForm1::FindStartOfNextTextRecord(int LineNumber, bool OnlyTopTerms)
{
    int Counter = LineNumber;
    int ReturnValue = InputLines->Count;

    if(Counter < 0)
        Counter = 0;

    if(Counter < InputLines->Count)
    {
        WideString String;

        String = InputLines->Strings[Counter];
        RemoveSpace((WideString *)&String);

        if(RadioButton7->Checked)
        {
            while(!String.IsEmpty() && Counter) && Counter < InputLines->Count - 1)
            {
                String = InputLines->Strings[++Counter];
                RemoveSpace((WideString *)&String);
            }
            while(String.IsEmpty() && Counter < InputLines->Count - 1)
            {
                String = InputLines->Strings[++Counter];
                RemoveSpace((WideString *)&String);
            }
            ReturnValue = Counter;
        }
        else if(RadioButton6->Checked)
        {
            while(WideCompareText(TntEdit14->Text, String) && Counter < InputLines->Count - 1)

```

```
    {
        /*if(Counter >= InputLines->Count - 1)
        {
            ++Counter;
            break;
        }*/
        String = InputLines->Strings[++Counter];
        RemoveSpace((WideString *)&String);
    }
    ReturnValue = Counter;
}
else if(RadioButton5->Checked)
{
    while(!IsStartedWith(String, TntEdit15->Text) && Counter < InputLines->Count - 1)
    {
        String = InputLines->Strings[++Counter];
        RemoveSpace((WideString *)&String);
    }
    ReturnValue = Counter;
}
}
```

```
return ReturnValue;
```

```
}
//-----
```

```
bool __fastcall TForm1::IsStartedWith(WideString String, WideString SearchString)
```

```
{
    if(AnsiStrPosICW(String, SearchString))
        return true;
    else
        return false;
}
```

```
//-----
```

```
void __fastcall TForm1::ResetRecord(Record *Rec)
```

```
{
    Rec->MT.Empty();
    Rec->BT.Empty();
    Rec->NT.Empty();
    Rec->RT.Empty();
    Rec->USE.Empty();
    Rec->UF.Empty();
    Rec->SN.Empty();
    Rec->HN.Empty();
    Rec->IND.Empty();
    Rec->Frq.Empty();
    Rec->SC.Empty();
    Rec->T1.Empty();
    Rec->T2.Empty();
    Rec->T3.Empty();
}
```

```
//-----
```

```
void __fastcall TForm1::SaveRecord(Fbtree *TreeFile, Record *Rec, bool AddToSub)
```

```
{  
    WideString Buffer;  
    char *FileBuffer;  
    RecordHeader RecHeader;
```

```
    RemoveSpace((WideString *)&Rec->MT);  
    RemoveSpace((WideString *)&Rec->BT);  
    RemoveSpace((WideString *)&Rec->NT);  
    RemoveSpace((WideString *)&Rec->RT);  
    RemoveSpace((WideString *)&Rec->USE);  
    RemoveSpace((WideString *)&Rec->UF);  
    RemoveSpace((WideString *)&Rec->SN);  
    RemoveSpace((WideString *)&Rec->HN);  
    RemoveSpace((WideString *)&Rec->IND);  
    RemoveSpace((WideString *)&Rec->Frq);  
    RemoveSpace((WideString *)&Rec->SC);  
    RemoveSpace((WideString *)&Rec->T1);  
    RemoveSpace((WideString *)&Rec->T2);  
    RemoveSpace((WideString *)&Rec->T3);
```

```
    RecHeader.MTLen = Rec->MT.Length();  
    RecHeader.BTLen = Rec->BT.Length();  
    RecHeader.NTLen = Rec->NT.Length();  
    RecHeader.RTLen = Rec->RT.Length();  
    RecHeader.USELen = Rec->USE.Length();  
    RecHeader.UFLen = Rec->UF.Length();  
    RecHeader.SNLen = Rec->SN.Length();  
    RecHeader.HNLen = Rec->HN.Length();  
    RecHeader.INDLen = Rec->IND.Length();  
    RecHeader.FrqLen = Rec->Frq.Length();  
    RecHeader.SCLen = Rec->SC.Length();  
    RecHeader.T1Len = Rec->T1.Length();  
    RecHeader.T2Len = Rec->T2.Length();  
    RecHeader.T3Len = Rec->T3.Length();
```

```
    *RecHeader.MT = 0;  
    if(!Rec->MT.IsEmpty())  
        wcscpy(RecHeader.MT, Rec->MT);
```

```
    Buffer.Empty();  
    Buffer.Insert(Rec->MT, Buffer.Length() + 1);  
    Buffer.Insert(Rec->BT, Buffer.Length() + 1);  
    Buffer.Insert(Rec->NT, Buffer.Length() + 1);  
    Buffer.Insert(Rec->RT, Buffer.Length() + 1);  
    Buffer.Insert(Rec->USE, Buffer.Length() + 1);  
    Buffer.Insert(Rec->UF, Buffer.Length() + 1);  
    Buffer.Insert(Rec->SN, Buffer.Length() + 1);  
    Buffer.Insert(Rec->HN, Buffer.Length() + 1);  
    Buffer.Insert(Rec->IND, Buffer.Length() + 1);  
    Buffer.Insert(Rec->Frq, Buffer.Length() + 1);  
    Buffer.Insert(Rec->SC, Buffer.Length() + 1);
```

```

Buffer.Insert(Rec->T1, Buffer.Length() + 1);
Buffer.Insert(Rec->T2, Buffer.Length() + 1);
Buffer.Insert(Rec->T3, Buffer.Length() + 1);

FileBuffer = new char[Buffer.Length() * sizeof(wchar_t) + sizeof(RecordHeader)];
memmove(FileBuffer, &RecHeader, sizeof(RecordHeader));
memmove(FileBuffer + sizeof(RecordHeader), Buffer.c_bstr(), Buffer.Length() * sizeof(wchar_t));

if(AddToSub)
    TreeFile->AddSubNode(FileBuffer, Buffer.Length() * sizeof(wchar_t) + sizeof(RecordHeader),
                        (char *)FileBuffer, 200);
else
    TreeFile->AddNode(FileBuffer, Buffer.Length() * sizeof(wchar_t) + sizeof(RecordHeader),
                    (char *)FileBuffer, 200);

delete[] FileBuffer;
}
//-----

```

```

void __fastcall TForm1::LoadRecord(Fbtree *TreeFile, Record *Rec)
{
    wchar_t *FileBuffer;
    wchar_t *Buffer;
    wchar_t *Pos;
    RecordHeader RecHeader;

    ResetRecord(Rec);
    FileBuffer = (wchar_t *)TreeFile->AllocGetCurrentNode(FileBuffer);

    memmove(&RecHeader, FileBuffer, sizeof(RecordHeader));
    (char *)Pos = (char *)FileBuffer + sizeof(RecordHeader);

    if(RecHeader.MTLen)
    {
        WideCopy((WideString *)&Rec->MT, Pos, RecHeader.MTLen);
        Pos += RecHeader.MTLen;
    }

    if(RecHeader.BTLen)
    {
        WideCopy((WideString *)&Rec->BT, Pos, RecHeader.BTLen);
        Pos += RecHeader.BTLen;
    }

    if(RecHeader.NTLen)
    {
        WideCopy((WideString *)&Rec->NT, Pos, RecHeader.NTLen);
        Pos += RecHeader.NTLen;
    }

    if(RecHeader.RTLen)
    {
        WideCopy((WideString *)&Rec->RT, Pos, RecHeader.RTLen);
    }
}

```

```
    Pos += RecHeader.RTLen;
}

if(RecHeader.USELen)
{
    WideCopy((WideString *)&Rec->USE, Pos, RecHeader.USELen);
    Pos += RecHeader.USELen;
}

if(RecHeader.UFLen)
{
    WideCopy((WideString *)&Rec->UF, Pos, RecHeader.UFLen);
    Pos += RecHeader.UFLen;
}

if(RecHeader.SNLen)
{
    WideCopy((WideString *)&Rec->SN, Pos, RecHeader.SNLen);
    Pos += RecHeader.SNLen;
}

if(RecHeader.HNLen)
{
    WideCopy((WideString *)&Rec->HN, Pos, RecHeader.HNLen);
    Pos += RecHeader.HNLen;
}

if(RecHeader.INDLen)
{
    WideCopy((WideString *)&Rec->IND, Pos, RecHeader.INDLen);
    Pos += RecHeader.INDLen;
}

if(RecHeader.FrqLen)
{
    WideCopy((WideString *)&Rec->Frq, Pos, RecHeader.FrqLen);
    Pos += RecHeader.FrqLen;
}

if(RecHeader.SCLen)
{
    WideCopy((WideString *)&Rec->SC, Pos, RecHeader.SCLen);
    Pos += RecHeader.SCLen;
}

if(RecHeader.T1Len)
{
    WideCopy((WideString *)&Rec->T1, Pos, RecHeader.T1Len);
    Pos += RecHeader.T1Len;
}

if(RecHeader.T2Len)
```

```

    {
        WideCopy((WideString *)&Rec->T2, Pos, RecHeader.T2Len);
        Pos += RecHeader.T2Len;
    }

    if(RecHeader.T3Len)
    {
        WideCopy((WideString *)&Rec->T3, Pos, RecHeader.T3Len);
        Pos += RecHeader.T3Len;
    }

    delete[] FileBuffer;
}
//-----

void __fastcall TForm1::MakeThesaurusStructure(void)
{
    Tree->Go(TOP);
    Record Rec;
    void *Result = Tree->FreeSearch(1, NULL, NULL, NULL, NULL);

    while(Result && !LoopEncountered)
    {
        LoadRecord(Tree, &Rec);
        Level = 0;
        SearchForNarrowerTerms(Rec);

        Result = Tree->FreeSearch(1, NULL, NULL, NULL, NULL, NEXT);
    }
}
//-----

void __fastcall TForm1::SearchForNarrowerTerms(Record Rec)
{
    TWideStringList *NTList = new TWideStringList;
    int LastPosition = Tree->CurrentNodeAddress;
    Record NewRecord;
    WideString String;

    ++Level;

    if(Level > 200)
    {
        LoopEncountered = true;
        MessageDlg("The Term " + Rec.MT + " or one of its broader terms encountered an unlimited " \
            "loop! Correct it and then try again.", mtError, TMsgDlgButtons() << mbOK, 0);
    }
    else
    {
        NTList->Text = Rec.NT;

        for(int i = 0; i < NTList->Count && !LoopEncountered; ++i)
        {

```

```

String = NTLList->Strings[i];
RemoveSpace((WideString *)&String);
Linear->Go(TOP);
if(Linear->BSearch(String))
{
    LoadRecord(Linear, &NewRecord);
    if(!i)
        SaveRecord(Tree, &NewRecord, true);
    else
    {
        Tree->Go(SUBTOP);
        SaveRecord(Tree, &NewRecord);
    }

    SearchForNarrowerTerms(NewRecord);
}
}

```

```

Tree->Go(LastPosition);
delete NTLList;

```

```
--Level;
```

```

}
//-----

```

```
bool __fastcall TForm1::IsIgnorableLine(WideString String)
```

```

{
    WideString SubString;

    for(int i = 0; i < TntMem01->Lines->Count; ++i)
    {
        SubString = TntMem01->Lines->Strings[i];
        RemoveSpace((WideString *)&SubString);
        if(IsStartedWith(String, SubString))
            return true;
    }

    return false;
}

```

```

}
//-----

```

```
void __fastcall TForm1::SendToMicrosoftAccess(void)
```

```

{
    AnsiString ConnectionString = "Provider=Microsoft.Jet.OLEDB.4.0;Data Source=" +
        SaveDialog1->FileName + ";Persist Security Info=False";
    AnsiString Fields = "LineNum Integer, "\
        "TermLevel Integer, "\
        "Term Char(100), "\
        "RT Memo, " \
        "SN Memo, " \
        "UF Memo, " \
        "USE Memo, " \

```

```

        "Translate1 Char(100), " \
        "Translate2 Char(100), " \
        "Translate3 Char(100), " \
        "Frequency Integer, " \
        "Description Memo, " \
        "InputDate Char(30), " \
        "SC Char(30), " \
        "HN Char(150), " \
        "Primary Key (LineNum)";

```

```
Application->ProcessMessages();
```

```

ADOQuery1->Close();
ADOQuery1->ConnectionString = "";
ADOTable1->Active = false;
ADOTable1->ConnectionString = "";
Application->ProcessMessages();

```

```

DeleteFile(SaveDialog1->FileName);
CreateAccessDatabase(SaveDialog1->FileName.c_str());
Application->ProcessMessages();

```

```
ADOQuery1->ConnectionString = ConnectionString;
```

```

ADOQuery1->SQL->Clear();
ADOQuery1->SQL->Add("Create Table Thesaurus (" + Fields + ");");
ADOQuery1->ExecSQL();

```

```

ADOQuery1->SQL->Clear();
ADOQuery1->SQL->Add("Create Table NPTerms (" + Fields + ");");
ADOQuery1->ExecSQL();

```

```

ADOQuery1->Close();
ADOQuery1->ConnectionString = "";
ADOTable1->ConnectionString = ConnectionString;

```

```

Application->ProcessMessages();
Tree->Go(TOP);
AccessCounter = AccessLevel = 0;

```

```

if(!LoopEncountered)
    ExportToAccess();

```

```
ADOTable1->ConnectionString = "";
```

```
}
//-----
```

```
void __fastcall TForm1::ExportToAccess(void)
```

```
{
    void *Result;
    Record Rec;
```

```
if(!AccessLevel)
```

```

{
    ADOTable1->TableName = "Thesaurus";
    ADOTable1->Active = true;
}

++AccessLevel;

Tree->Go (SUBTOP);

Result = Tree->FreeSearch(AccessLevel, NULL, NULL, NULL, NULL);

while (Result)
{
    LoadRecord(Tree, &Rec);
    ReplaceWithTranslation(&Rec);

    ADOTable1->Append();
    ADOTable1->FieldByName("LineNum")->AsInteger = ++AccessCounter;
    ADOTable1->FieldByName("TermLevel")->AsInteger = AccessLevel - 1;
    ADOTable1->FieldByName("Term")->Value = Rec.MT;
    ADOTable1->FieldByName("RT")->Value = Rec.RT;
    ADOTable1->FieldByName("SN")->Value = Rec.SN;
    ADOTable1->FieldByName("UF")->Value = Rec.UF;
    ADOTable1->FieldByName("USE")->Value = Rec.USE;
    ADOTable1->FieldByName("Translate1")->Value = Rec.T1;
    ADOTable1->FieldByName("Translate2")->Value = Rec.T2;
    ADOTable1->FieldByName("Translate3")->Value = Rec.T3;
    ADOTable1->FieldByName("InputDate")->Value = Rec.IND;
    ADOTable1->FieldByName("SC")->Value = Rec.SC;
    ADOTable1->FieldByName("HN")->Value = Rec.HN;
    ADOTable1->FieldByName("Frequency")->AsInteger = StringToInt(Rec.Frq);
    ADOTable1->Post();

    if(Tree->Go (SUB))
        ExportToAccess();

    Result = Tree->FreeSearch(AccessLevel, NULL, NULL, NULL, NULL, NEXT);
    Application->ProcessMessages();
}

Tree->Go (MOTHER);
--AccessLevel;

if(!AccessLevel)
    ADOTable1->Active = false;
}

```

//-----

```

WideString __fastcall TForm1::TranslationOf(WideString String)
{

```

```

    WideString ReturnValue(String);

```

```

    if(!String.IsEmpty())

```

```

{
    Record Rec;
    WideString Translation;
    RemoveSpace((WideString *)&String);

    Linear->Go(TOP);
    if(Linear->BSearch(String))
    {
        LoadRecord(Linear, &Rec);

        if(RadioButton2->Checked)
            Translation = Rec.T1;
        else if(RadioButton3->Checked)
            Translation = Rec.T2;
        else if(RadioButton4->Checked)
            Translation = Rec.T3;

        if(!Translation.IsEmpty())
            ReturnValue = Translation;
    }

    return ReturnValue;
}

//-----

void __fastcall TForm1::ReplaceWithTranslation(Record *Rec)
{
    WideString MTBackup(Rec->MT);
    TWideStringList *List = new TWideStringList();

    if(!RadioButton1->Checked)
    {
        Rec->MT = TranslationOf(Rec->MT);
        if(WideCompareText(Rec->MT, MTBackup))
        {
            if(RadioButton2->Checked)
                Rec->T1 = MTBackup;
            else if(RadioButton3->Checked)
                Rec->T2 = MTBackup;
            else if(RadioButton4->Checked)
                Rec->T3 = MTBackup;
        }

        List->Text = Rec->RT;
        for(int i = 0; i < List->Count; ++i)
            List->Strings[i] = TranslationOf(List->Strings[i]);
        Rec->RT = List->Text;

        List->Text = Rec->USE;
        for(int i = 0; i < List->Count; ++i)
            List->Strings[i] = TranslationOf(List->Strings[i]);
        Rec->USE = List->Text;
    }
}

```

```
List->Text = Rec->UF;  
for(int i = 0; i < List->Count; ++i)  
    List->Strings[i] = TranslationOf(List->Strings[i]);  
Rec->UF = List->Text;
```

```
}
```

```
delete List;
```

```
}
```

```
//-----
```

```
object Form1: TForm1
  Left = 292
  Top = 330
  BiDiMode = bdRightToLeft
  BorderIcons = [biSystemMenu, biMinimize]
  BorderStyle = bsSingle
  Caption = 'تبدیل متن اصطلاحنامه'
  ClientHeight = 375
  ClientWidth = 674
  Color = clBtnFace
  Font.Charset = DEFAULT_CHARSET
  Font.Color = clWindowText
  Font.Height = -11
  Font.Name = 'Tahoma'
  Font.Style = []
  OldCreateOrder = False
  ParentBiDiMode = False
  Position = poScreenCenter
  PixelsPerInch = 96
  TextHeight = 13
  object Label1: TLabel
    Left = 70
    Top = 80
    Width = 164
    Height = 13
    Caption = 'نادیده گرفتن خطوط با نشانه‌های زیر:'
  end
  object GroupBox1: TGroupBox
    Left = 409
    Top = 8
    Width = 257
    Height = 345
    Caption = 'نشانه‌های فیلدها'
    TabOrder = 0
    object CheckBox1: TCheckBox
      Left = 144
      Top = 24
      Width = 97
      Height = 17
      Caption = 'عنوان اعم'
      Checked = True
      Enabled = False
      State = cbChecked
      TabOrder = 0
    end
    object CheckBox2: TCheckBox
      Left = 144
      Top = 48
      Width = 97
      Height = 17
      Caption = 'عنوان اخص'
      Checked = True
      Enabled = False
    end
  end
end
```

```
State = cbChecked
TabOrder = 1
end
object CheckBox3: TCheckBox
Left = 144
Top = 72
Width = 97
Height = 17
Caption = 'عنوان وابسته'
Checked = True
State = cbChecked
TabOrder = 2
end
object CheckBox4: TCheckBox
Left = 144
Top = 96
Width = 97
Height = 17
Caption = 'بکار برید'
Checked = True
State = cbChecked
TabOrder = 3
end
object CheckBox5: TCheckBox
Left = 144
Top = 120
Width = 97
Height = 17
Caption = 'جای'
Checked = True
State = cbChecked
TabOrder = 4
end
object CheckBox6: TCheckBox
Left = 144
Top = 144
Width = 97
Height = 17
Caption = 'یادداشت دامنه'
Checked = True
State = cbChecked
TabOrder = 5
end
object CheckBox7: TCheckBox
Left = 144
Top = 168
Width = 97
Height = 17
Caption = 'نارنجیه'
Checked = True
State = cbChecked
TabOrder = 6
end
end
```

```
object CheckBox8: TCheckBox
  Left = 144
  Top = 192
  Width = 97
  Height = 17
  Caption = 'تاریخ ورود'
  Checked = True
  State = cbChecked
  TabOrder = 7
```

end

```
object CheckBox9: TCheckBox
  Left = 144
  Top = 216
  Width = 97
  Height = 17
  Caption = 'بسامد'
  Checked = True
  State = cbChecked
  TabOrder = 8
```

end

```
object CheckBox10: TCheckBox
  Left = 136
  Top = 240
  Width = 105
  Height = 17
  Caption = 'رشته موضوعی'
  Checked = True
  State = cbChecked
  TabOrder = 9
```

end

```
object CheckBox11: TCheckBox
  Left = 144
  Top = 264
  Width = 97
  Height = 17
  Caption = 'ترجمه ۱'
  TabOrder = 10
```

end

```
object CheckBox12: TCheckBox
  Left = 144
  Top = 288
  Width = 97
  Height = 17
  Caption = 'ترجمه ۲'
  TabOrder = 11
```

end

```
object CheckBox13: TCheckBox
  Left = 144
  Top = 312
  Width = 97
  Height = 17
  Caption = 'ترجمه ۳'
  TabOrder = 12
```

```
end
object TntEdit1: TTntEdit
  Left = 16
  Top = 24
  Width = 121
  Height = 21
  TabOrder = 13
  Text = 'BT:'
end
object TntEdit2: TTntEdit
  Left = 16
  Top = 48
  Width = 121
  Height = 21
  TabOrder = 14
  Text = 'NT:'
end
object TntEdit3: TTntEdit
  Left = 16
  Top = 72
  Width = 121
  Height = 21
  TabOrder = 15
  Text = 'RT:'
end
object TntEdit4: TTntEdit
  Left = 16
  Top = 96
  Width = 121
  Height = 21
  TabOrder = 16
  Text = 'USE:'
end
object TntEdit5: TTntEdit
  Left = 16
  Top = 120
  Width = 121
  Height = 21
  TabOrder = 17
  Text = 'UF:'
end
object TntEdit6: TTntEdit
  Left = 16
  Top = 144
  Width = 121
  Height = 21
  TabOrder = 18
  Text = 'SN:'
end
object TntEdit7: TTntEdit
  Left = 16
  Top = 168
  Width = 121
```

```
    Height = 21
    TabOrder = 19
    Text = 'HN:'
end
object TntEdit8: TTntEdit
    Left = 16
    Top = 192
    Width = 121
    Height = 21
    TabOrder = 20
    Text = 'IND:'
end
object TntEdit9: TTntEdit
    Left = 16
    Top = 216
    Width = 121
    Height = 21
    TabOrder = 21
    Text = 'Frq:'
end
object TntEdit10: TTntEdit
    Left = 16
    Top = 240
    Width = 121
    Height = 21
    TabOrder = 22
    Text = 'SC:'
end
object TntEdit11: TTntEdit
    Left = 16
    Top = 264
    Width = 121
    Height = 21
    TabOrder = 23
end
object TntEdit13: TTntEdit
    Left = 16
    Top = 312
    Width = 121
    Height = 21
    TabOrder = 24
end
object TntEdit12: TTntEdit
    Left = 16
    Top = 288
    Width = 121
    Height = 21
    TabOrder = 25
end
object LabeledEdit1: TLabeledEdit
    Left = 88
    Top = 16
```

```
Width = 234
Height = 21
EditLabel.Width = 70
EditLabel.Height = 13
EditLabel.BiDiMode = bdRightToLeft
EditLabel.Caption = 'نام فایل ورودی'
EditLabel.ParentBiDiMode = False
LabelPosition = lpRight
LabelSpacing = 10
TabOrder = 1
```

end

```
object Button1: TButton
```

```
Left = 7
Top = 16
Width = 75
Height = 25
Caption = 'دیسک...'
TabOrder = 2
OnClick = Button1Click
```

end

```
object GroupBox2: TGroupBox
```

```
Left = 241
Top = 80
Width = 161
Height = 153
Caption = 'نشانه آغاز یک رکورد'
TabOrder = 5
```

```
object TntEdit14: TTntEdit
```

```
Left = 8
Top = 64
Width = 121
Height = 21
TabOrder = 2
Text = 'Record:'
```

end

```
object TntEdit15: TTntEdit
```

```
Left = 8
Top = 112
Width = 121
Height = 21
TabOrder = 4
Text = 'MT:'
```

end

```
object RadioButton5: TRadioButton
```

```
Left = 16
Top = 94
Width = 137
Height = 17
Caption = 'نشانه واژه اصلی'
TabOrder = 3
```

end

```
object RadioButton6: TRadioButton
```

```
Left = 40
```

```
    Top = 46
    Width = 113
    Height = 17
    Caption = 'خطي شامل:'
    TabOrder = 1
end
object RadioButton7: TRadioButton
    Left = 40
    Top = 22
    Width = 113
    Height = 17
    Caption = 'خط خالي'
    Checked = True
    TabOrder = 0
    TabStop = True
end
end
object LabeledEdit2: TLabeledEdit
    Left = 88
    Top = 48
    Width = 234
    Height = 21
    EditLabel.Width = 73
    EditLabel.Height = 13
    EditLabel.BiDiMode = bdRightToLeft
    EditLabel.Caption = 'نام فايل خروجي'
    EditLabel.ParentBiDiMode = False
    LabelPosition = lpRight
    LabelSpacing = 3
    TabOrder = 3
end
end
object Button2: TButton
    Left = 7
    Top = 48
    Width = 75
    Height = 25
    Caption = '...ديسك'
    TabOrder = 4
   OnClick = Button2Click
end
end
object Button3: TButton
    Left = 7
    Top = 328
    Width = 226
    Height = 25
    Caption = 'تبدیل'
    TabOrder = 8
   OnClick = Button3Click
end
end
object TntMemo1: TTntMemo
    Left = 8
    Top = 96
    Width = 226
```

```
Height = 225
TabOrder = 7
end
object GroupBox3: TGroupBox
Left = 241
Top = 248
Width = 161
Height = 105
Caption = 'جاڭگزيني زبان اصلي با'
TabOrder = 6
object RadioButton1: TRadioButton
Left = 32
Top = 24
Width = 113
Height = 17
Caption = 'عدم جاڭگزيني'
Checked = True
TabOrder = 0
TabStop = True
end
object RadioButton2: TRadioButton
Left = 32
Top = 40
Width = 113
Height = 17
Caption = '\ ترجمه'
TabOrder = 1
end
object RadioButton3: TRadioButton
Left = 32
Top = 56
Width = 113
Height = 17
Caption = '\ ترجمه'
TabOrder = 2
end
object RadioButton4: TRadioButton
Left = 32
Top = 72
Width = 113
Height = 17
Caption = '\ ترجمه'
TabOrder = 3
end
end
object StatusBar1: TStatusBar
Left = 0
Top = 356
Width = 674
Height = 19
Panels = <>
SimplePanel = True
SimpleText = #9#9#9#9
```

```
end
object OpenDialog1: TOpenDialog
  DefaultExt = 'txt'
  Filter = 'Text files (*.txt)|*.txt|All files (*.*)|*.*'
  Options = [ofReadOnly, ofPathMustExist, ofFileMustExist, ofEnableSizing]
  Left = 197
  Top = 112
end
object SaveDialog1: TSaveDialog
  DefaultExt = 'mdb'
  Filter = 'MS-Access Database (*.mdb)|*.mdb'
  Options = [ofOverwritePrompt, ofHideReadOnly, ofPathMustExist, ofEnableSizing]
  Left = 165
  Top = 112
end
object ADOQuery1: TADOQuery
  CursorLocation = clUseServer
  Parameters = <>
  Left = 165
  Top = 144
end
object ADOTable1: TADOTable
  Left = 197
  Top = 144
end
end
```

```
//-----  
#ifndef ProcessH  
#define ProcessH  
//-----  
#include <Classes.hpp>  
#include <Controls.hpp>  
#include <StdCtrls.hpp>  
#include <Forms.hpp>  
#include "TntStdCtrls.hpp"  
#include <ExtCtrls.hpp>  
#include <Dialogs.hpp>  
#include "WFbtree.h"  
#include <ADODB.hpp>  
#include <DB.hpp>  
#include <ComCtrls.hpp>  
//-----  
  
#define ADDWITHSEPARATOR(a, b) { \                                \  
    if (!a.IsEmpty()) \                                           \  
        (a) += "\r\n"; \                                           \  
    (a) += (b); \                                                    \  
} \                                                                    \  
  
typedef enum {MT = 1, BT, NT, RT, USE, UF, SN, HN, IND, Frq, SC, T1, T2, T3} ThesaurusFields;  
  
struct RecordHeader  
{  
    wchar_t MT[101];  
    int MLen;  
    int BLen;  
    int NLen;  
    int RLen;  
    int USELen;  
    int ULen;  
    int SNLen;  
    int HNLen;  
    int INLen;  
    int FrqLen;  
    int SCLen;  
    int T1Len;  
    int T2Len;  
    int T3Len;  
};  
  
struct Record  
{  
    WideString MT;  
    WideString BT;  
    WideString NT;  
    WideString RT;  
    WideString USE;  
    WideString UF;  
};
```

```
WideString SN;  
WideString HN;  
WideString IND;  
WideString Frq;  
WideString SC;  
WideString T1;  
WideString T2;  
WideString T3;
```

```
};
```

```
class TForm1 : public TForm
```

```
{  
    published:    // IDE-managed Components  
    TGroupBox *GroupBox1;  
    TCheckBox *CheckBox1;  
    TCheckBox *CheckBox2;  
    TCheckBox *CheckBox3;  
    TCheckBox *CheckBox4;  
    TCheckBox *CheckBox5;  
    TCheckBox *CheckBox6;  
    TCheckBox *CheckBox7;  
    TCheckBox *CheckBox8;  
    TCheckBox *CheckBox9;  
    TCheckBox *CheckBox10;  
    TCheckBox *CheckBox11;  
    TCheckBox *CheckBox12;  
    TCheckBox *CheckBox13;  
    TTntEdit *TntEdit1;  
    TTntEdit *TntEdit2;  
    TTntEdit *TntEdit3;  
    TTntEdit *TntEdit4;  
    TTntEdit *TntEdit5;  
    TTntEdit *TntEdit6;  
    TTntEdit *TntEdit7;  
    TTntEdit *TntEdit8;  
    TTntEdit *TntEdit9;  
    TTntEdit *TntEdit10;  
    TTntEdit *TntEdit11;  
    TTntEdit *TntEdit13;  
    TLabelledEdit *LabelledEdit1;  
    TButton *Button1;  
    TGroupBox *GroupBox2;  
    TTntEdit *TntEdit14;  
    TTntEdit *TntEdit15;  
    TLabelledEdit *LabelledEdit2;  
    TButton *Button2;  
    TOpenDialog *OpenDialog1;  
    TSaveDialog *SaveDialog1;  
    TTntEdit *TntEdit12;  
    TButton *Button3;  
    TTntMemo *TntMemo1;  
    TLabel *Label1;
```

```

TGroupBox *GroupBox3;
TRadioButton *RadioButton1;
TRadioButton *RadioButton2;
TRadioButton *RadioButton3;
TRadioButton *RadioButton4;
TADOQuery *ADOQuery1;
TADOTable *ADOTable1;
TRadioButton *RadioButton5;
TRadioButton *RadioButton6;
TRadioButton *RadioButton7;
TStatusBar *StatusBar1;
void __fastcall Button1Click(TObject *Sender);
void __fastcall Button2Click(TObject *Sender);
void __fastcall Button3Click(TObject *Sender);
private: // User declarations
TWideStringList *InputLines;
int CountLines;
Fbtree *Tree;
Fbtree *Linear;
int Level;
int AccessLevel;
int AccessCounter;
bool LoopEncountered;

void __fastcall FindTopTerms(void);
void __fastcall FindAllTerms(void);
void __fastcall MakeThesaurusStructure(void);
bool __fastcall FindTextRecord(Record *Rec, int LineNumber = 0, bool OnlyTopTerms = false);
int __fastcall FindStartOfNextTextRecord(int LineNumber = 0, bool OnlyTopTerms = false);
bool __fastcall IsStartedWith(WideString String, WideString SearchString);
void __fastcall ResetRecord(Record *Rec);
void __fastcall SaveRecord(Fbtree *TreeFile, Record *Rec, bool AddToSub = false);
void __fastcall LoadRecord(Fbtree *TreeFile, Record *Rec);
void __fastcall SearchForNarrowerTerms(Record Rec);
bool __fastcall IsIgnorableLine(WideString String);
void __fastcall SendToMicrosoftAccess(void);
void __fastcall ExportToAccess(void);
void __fastcall ReplaceWithTranslation(Record *Rec);
WideString __fastcall TranslationOf(WideString String);

public: // User declarations
__fastcall TForm1(TComponent* Owner);
};
//-----
extern PACKAGE TForm1 *Form1;
//-----
#endif

```

```

#include <vcl.h>
#pragma hdrstop

#include "stdio.h"
#include "WFBtree.h"

#pragma package(smart_init)
//-----

struct DateSpec
{
    int year;
    char month, day;
    char dayofweek;
};

char fbtree_currentindex_sign;
AnsiString ExecutionPath;
//-----

long date_unique_number(DateSpec *date)
{
    return (long)date->year * 372 + (date->month - 1) * 31 + (date->day - 1);
}
//-----

bool __fastcall _DeleteFile(const AnsiString FileName, bool UseExecutionPath)
{
    AnsiString FileNamePath = FileName;
    bool returnval;

    if(UseExecutionPath)
        FileNamePath.Insert(ExecutionPath, 1);

    if(FileExists(FileNamePath))
        returnval = DeleteFile(FileNamePath);
    else
        returnval = true;

    return returnval;
}
//-----

bool __fastcall _FileExists(const AnsiString FileName, bool UseExecutionPath)
{
    AnsiString FileNamePath = FileName;
    bool returnval;

    FileNamePath.Insert(ExecutionPath, 1);
    returnval = FileExists(FileNamePath);

    return returnval;
}

```

```
//-----
```

```
Fbtree::Fbtree(char *Filename, bool change_header, bool casesens, int (*comp)(WideString s1, WideString s2, unsigned len), FbtreeIndex *f_index, bool use_execpath, bool OpenIndexes)
{
    register i;

    UseExecutionPath = use_execpath;
    ExecutionPath = UseExecutionPath ? (GetExecutionPath() + "\\") : String("");

    record_preview.LeftAddress = record_preview.RightAddress = record_preview.SubNodeAddress = record_preview.MotherNodeAddress =
    record_preview.PreviousNodeAddress = NULL;
    CaseSensitive = casesens;

    for(register i = 0; i <= MAXFBTREELEVEL; i++)
    {
        LastSearchedAddress[i] = NULL;
        Stack[i] = new int[1];
        StackPosition[i] = 0;
    }

    CompareFunction = comp;
    OpenAllIndexes = OpenIndexes;

    FbtreeHeader head = {"HUF Data File", 26, "Œœ'-'", "Œœ'-'", 0, {0}, 0.0, {0}, {0}};

    if(change_header == YES)
        *head.Security1 = *head.Security2 = 0;

    Header = head;

    StrCopy(FbtreeFilename, Filename);

    OptimizeActive = NO;
    CurrentFileLevel = 1;
    OpenIndexFlag = 0;

    Found = _FileExists(Filename, UseExecutionPath);

    if(Found)
        Mode = fmOpenReadWrite;
    else
        Mode = fmCreate;

    File = new TFileStream(ExecutionPath + Filename, Mode);

    if(File->Handle > 0)
    {
        if(Found == false)
            WriteHeader();
    }

    for(i = 0; i < MAXFBTREEINDEX; i++)
```

```
    Index[i] = NULL;

fbtree_index = NULL;
IndexCounter = 0;
if(f_index)
{
    while(f_index[IndexCounter].Filename && IndexCounter < MAXFBTREEINDEX)
        IndexCounter++;

    if(IndexCounter)
        fbtree_index = new FbtreeIndex[IndexCounter + 1];

    for(i = 0; i < IndexCounter; i++)
    {
        fbtree_index[i].Filename = new char[strlen(f_index[i].Filename) + 1];
        StrCopy(fbtree_index[i].Filename, f_index[i].Filename);

        fbtree_index[i].Level = f_index[i].Level;
        fbtree_index[i].StartKey = f_index[i].StartKey;
        fbtree_index[i].Len = f_index[i].Len;
        fbtree_index[i].Comp = f_index[i].Comp;
        fbtree_index[i].CompareKind = f_index[i].Comp ? fbtFREECOMPARE : f_index[i].CompareKind;
        fbtree_index[i].Sign = f_index[i].Sign;
    }
    fbtree_index[IndexCounter].Filename = NULL;
}

if(File->Handle > 0)
{
    ReadHeader();
    GetNextNewNodeAddress();
    CurrentNodeAddress = Header.FirstNodeAddress;
}

if(OpenAllIndexes)
    OpenIndexFiles();

ProgressBar = NULL;
}
//-----

Fbtree::~Fbtree(void)
{
    CloseIndexFiles(true);

    if(IndexCounter)
    {
        for(register i = IndexCounter - 1; i >= 0; i--)
            delete[] fbtree_index[i].Filename;

        delete[] fbtree_index;
    }
}
```

```
delete File;
```

```
for(register i = MAXFBTREELEVEL; i >= 0; i--)  
    if(Stack[i])  
        delete[] Stack[i];
```

```
}  
//-----
```

```
void Fbtree::GetNextNewNodeAddress(void)
```

```
{  
    NewNodeAddress = File->Size;  
}  
//-----
```

```
void Fbtree::WriteNewRecord(void *nodestruct)
```

```
{  
    if(File->Handle > 0)  
    {  
        File->Seek(NewNodeAddress, soFromBeginning);  
        File->Write(&record_preview, sizeof(RecordPreview));  
        File->Write(nodestruct, record_preview.RecordLen);  
        CurrentNodeAddress = NewNodeAddress;  
  
        GetNextNewNodeAddress();  
    }  
}  
//-----
```

```
void Fbtree::WriteHeader(char *source, int start, int size)
```

```
{  
    if(File->Handle > 0)  
    {  
        if(source)  
        {  
            char *ptr = (char *)&Header;  
  
            ptr += start;  
  
            for(register i = 0; i < size; i++)  
                *ptr++ = *(source + i);  
        }  
  
        File->Seek(0, soFromBeginning);  
        File->Write(&Header, sizeof(FbtreeHeader));  
    }  
}  
//-----
```

```
void Fbtree::ReadHeader(char *dest, int start, int size)
```

```
{  
    if(File->Handle > 0)  
    {  
        File->Seek(0, soFromBeginning);
```

```
File->Read(&Header, sizeof(FbtreeHeader));

if(dest)
{
    char *ptr = (char *)&Header;

    ptr += start;

    for(register i = 0; i < size; i++)
        *dest++ = *(ptr + i);
}
}
}
//-----

void Fbtree::ReadRecord(void *nodestruct, long nodeaddress)
{
    if(File->Handle > 0)
    {
        if(nodeaddress == -1)
            nodeaddress = CurrentNodeAddress;

        File->Seek(nodeaddress, soFromBeginning);
        File->Read(&record_preview, sizeof(RecordPreview));
        File->Read(nodestruct, record_preview.RecordLen);
    }
}
//-----

void *Fbtree::AllocGetCurrentNode(void *nodestruct)
{
    return nodestruct = (char *)AllocReadRecord(nodestruct, CurrentNodeAddress);
}
//-----

void *Fbtree::AllocReadRecord(void *nodestruct, long nodeaddress)
{
    void *ReturnValue = NULL;

    if(File->Handle > 0)
    {
        if(nodeaddress == -1)
            nodeaddress = CurrentNodeAddress;

        File->Seek(nodeaddress, soFromBeginning);
        File->Read(&record_preview, sizeof(RecordPreview));

        ReturnValue = nodestruct = new char[record_preview.RecordLen + 2];

        if(nodestruct)
            File->Read(nodestruct, record_preview.RecordLen);
        *((char *)nodestruct + record_preview.RecordLen) = 0;
    }
}
```

```
    return ReturnValue;
}
//-----
int Fbtree::Compare(void *comp1, void *comp2, unsigned size, char CompareKind)
{
    int ReturnValue;

    if(CompareKind == fbtFREECOMPARE)
        if(CompareFunction)
            ReturnValue = CompareFunction((wchar_t *)comp1, (wchar_t *)comp2, size);
        else
            CompareKind = fbtSTRING;

    if(CompareKind != fbtFREECOMPARE)
        switch(CompareKind)
        {
            case fbtSTRING:
                if(CaseSensitive)
                    ReturnValue = wcsncmp((wchar_t *)comp1, (wchar_t *)comp2, size);
                else
                    ReturnValue = _wcsnicmp((wchar_t *)comp1, (wchar_t *)comp2, size);
                break;

            case fbtCHAR:
                ReturnValue = *(wchar_t *)comp1 > *(wchar_t *)comp2 ? 1 : *(wchar_t *)comp1 == *(wchar_t *)comp2 ? 0 : -1;
                break;

            case fbtINTEGER:
                ReturnValue = *(int *)comp1 > *(int *)comp2 ? 1 : *(int *)comp1 == *(int *)comp2 ? 0 : -1;
                break;

            case fbtLONG:
                ReturnValue = *(long *)comp1 > *(long *)comp2 ? 1 : *(long *)comp1 == *(long *)comp2 ? 0 : -1;
                break;

            case fbtFLOAT:
                ReturnValue = *(float *)comp1 > *(float *)comp2 ? 1 : *(float *)comp1 == *(float *)comp2 ? 0 : -1;
                break;

            case fbtDOUBLE:
                ReturnValue = *(double *)comp1 > *(double *)comp2 ? 1 : *(double *)comp1 == *(double *)comp2 ? 0 : -1;
                break;

            case fbtDATE:
                ReturnValue = date_unique_number((DateSpec *)comp1) > date_unique_number((DateSpec *)comp2) ? 1 :
                date_unique_number((DateSpec *)comp1) == date_unique_number((DateSpec *)comp2) ? 0 : -1;
                break;
        }

    return ReturnValue;
}
```

```
//-----  
char Fbtree::AddNode(void *nodestruct, int nodestructsize, void *startnodekey, int keysize, char CompareKind, int nodeaddress)  
{  
    wchar_t *readnode = NULL, *readnodebak;  
    char ReturnValue = 0;  
    int comparevalue;  
  
    if(File->Handle > 0)  
    {  
        OpenIndexFiles();  
  
        record_preview.RecordLen = (unsigned)nodestructsize;  
        record_preview.KeyStartAddress = (unsigned)((char *)startnodekey - (char *)nodestruct);  
        record_preview.KeyLen = (unsigned)keysize;  
        record_preview.CompareKind = CompareKind;  
  
        if(nodeaddress > 0)  
        {  
            File->Seek(nodeaddress, soFromBeginning);  
            CurrentNodeAddress = nodeaddress;  
        }  
  
        if(!Header.FirstNodeAddress)  
        {  
            record_preview.LeftAddress =  
            record_preview.RightAddress =  
            record_preview.SubNodeAddress =  
            record_preview.MotherNodeAddress =  
            record_preview.PreviousNodeAddress = 0;  
  
            Header.FirstNodeAddress = CurrentNodeAddress = NewNodeAddress;  
            WriteHeader();  
            WriteNewRecord(nodestruct);  
  
            WriteIndex(nodestruct);  
        }  
        else  
        {  
            PreviousNodeAddress = CurrentNodeAddress;  
            if(!nodeaddress)  
            {  
                record_preview.LeftAddress = record_preview.RightAddress = record_preview.SubNodeAddress = NULL;  
                record_preview.PreviousNodeAddress = PreviousNodeAddress;  
                WriteNewRecord(nodestruct);  
                WriteIndex(nodestruct);  
  
                File->Seek(PreviousNodeAddress, soFromBeginning);  
                File->Read(&record_preview, sizeof(RecordPreview));  
  
                switch(PreviousPath)  
                {  
                    case LEFT:
```

```

        record_preview.LeftAddress = CurrentNodeAddress;
        break;

    case RIGHT:
        record_preview.RightAddress = CurrentNodeAddress;
        break;
}

File->Seek(PreviousNodeAddress, soFromBeginning);
File->Write(&record_preview, sizeof(RecordPreview));

ReturnValue = 1;
}
else
{
    readnode = (wchar_t *)AllocReadRecord(readnode, CurrentNodeAddress);
    readnodebak = readnode;
    (char *)readnode += (unsigned)((char *)startnodekey - (char *)nodestruct);

    comparevalue = Compare(startnodekey, readnode, keysize, CompareKind);

    if(readnode)
    {
        readnode = readnodebak;
        delete[] readnode;
    }

    if(comparevalue <= 0)
    {
        PreviousPath = LEFT;
        ReturnValue = AddNode(nodestruct, nodestructsize, startnodekey, keysize, CompareKind, record_preview.LeftAddress);
    }
    else
    {
        PreviousPath = RIGHT;
        ReturnValue = AddNode(nodestruct, nodestructsize, startnodekey, keysize, CompareKind, record_preview.RightAddress);
    }
}
}

CloseIndexFiles();
}

return ReturnValue;
}
//-----

```

```

char Fbtree::AddSubNode(void *nodestruct, int nodestructsize, void *startnodekey, int keysize, char CompareKind, int nodeaddress)
{
    wchar_t *readnode = new wchar_t[nodestructsize + 1], *readnodebak = readnode;
    char ReturnValue = 0;

    if(readnode && File->Handle > 0)

```

```
{
    if (Header.FirstNodeAddress)
    {
        CurrentFileLevel++;

        OpenIndexFiles();

        File->Seek(CurrentNodeAddress, soFromBeginning);
        File->Read(&record_preview, sizeof(RecordPreview));

        if (record_preview.SubNodeAddress)
            ReturnValue = AddNode(nodestruct, nodestructsize, startnodekey, keysize, CompareKind, record_preview.SubNodeAddress);
        else
        {
            ReturnValue = 1;

            record_preview.RecordLen = (unsigned)nodestructsize;
            record_preview.KeyStartAddress = (unsigned)((char *)startnodekey - (char *)nodestruct);
            record_preview.KeyLen = (unsigned)keysize;
            record_preview.CompareKind = CompareKind;

            if (nodeaddress > 0)
            {
                File->Seek(nodeaddress, soFromBeginning);
                CurrentNodeAddress = nodeaddress;
            }

            PreviousNodeAddress = CurrentNodeAddress;

            record_preview.LeftAddress = record_preview.RightAddress = record_preview.SubNodeAddress =
record_preview.PreviousNodeAddress = NULL;
            record_preview.MotherNodeAddress = PreviousNodeAddress;
            WriteNewRecord(nodestruct);
            WriteIndex(nodestruct);

            File->Seek(PreviousNodeAddress, soFromBeginning);
            File->Read(&record_preview, sizeof(RecordPreview));

            record_preview.SubNodeAddress = CurrentNodeAddress;

            File->Seek(PreviousNodeAddress, soFromBeginning);
            File->Write(&record_preview, sizeof(RecordPreview));

        }

        CloseIndexFiles();
    }
    else
        ReturnValue = AddNode(nodestruct, nodestructsize, startnodekey, keysize, CompareKind, nodeaddress);
}

if (readnode)
{
```

```

        readnode = readnodebak;
        delete[] readnode;
    }

    return ReturnValue;
}
//-----
char Fbtree::GetCurrentNode(void *nodestruct)
{
    char ReturnValue = 0;

    if(Header.FirstNodeAddress)
    {
        ReadRecord(nodestruct);
        ReturnValue = 1;
    }

    return ReturnValue;
}
//-----
void *Fbtree::BSearch(void *searchstring, int startaddress)
{
    void *ReturnValue = NULL;
    int comparevalue;

    if(Header.FirstNodeAddress && File->Handle > 0)
    {
        if(startaddress == -1)
        {
            startaddress = CurrentNodeAddress;
        }

        wchar_t *readnode = NULL, *readnodebak;
        readnode = (wchar_t *)AllocReadRecord(readnode, startaddress);
        readnodebak = readnode;
        (char *)readnode += record_preview.KeyStartAddress;

        comparevalue = Compare(searchstring, readnode, record_preview.KeyLen, record_preview.CompareKind);

        if(!comparevalue)
        {
            CurrentNodeAddress = startaddress;
            ReturnValue = readnodebak;
        }
        else
        {
            readnode = readnodebak;
            delete[] readnode;
            readnode = NULL;

            if(comparevalue > 0)

```

```
    {
        if(record_preview.RightAddress)
            ReturnValue = BSearch(searchstring, record_preview.RightAddress);
    }
    else
    {
        if(record_preview.LeftAddress)
            ReturnValue = BSearch(searchstring, record_preview.LeftAddress);
    }
}

if(readnode)
{
    readnode = readnodebak;
    delete[] readnode;
}
}
```

```
return ReturnValue;
```

```
}
//-----
```

```
void *Fbtree::FreeSearch(int searchlevel, void *searchstring, void *nodestruct, void *compareaddress, unsigned comparelen, char firstornext,
char CompareKind)
```

```
{
    searchlevel--;

    void *ReturnValue = NULL;
    int comparevalue;
    bool done = false;
    char first_next = firstornext;
    int PopAddress, CurrentNodeAddressbak = CurrentNodeAddress;
    RecordPreview rpsave;

    if(File->Handle > 0 && Header.FirstNodeAddress && (firstornext == FIRST || (firstornext == NEXT && LastSearchedAddress[searchlevel])))
    {
        if(firstornext == NEXT)
            Go(LastSearchedAddress[searchlevel]);
        else
            StackPosition[searchlevel] = 0;

        File->Seek(CurrentNodeAddress, soFromBeginning);
        File->Read(&record_preview, sizeof(RecordPreview));

        wchar_t *readnode = NULL, *readnodebak;

        readnode = (wchar_t *)AllocReadRecord(readnode, CurrentNodeAddress);
        readnodebak = readnode;

        rpsave = record_preview;

        while(!done && readnode)
        {
```

```
if(rpsave.LeftAddress && first_next == FIRST)
{
    if(!Push(CurrentNodeAddress, searchlevel))
        break;
    Go(LEFT);
    readnode = readnodebak;
    delete[] readnode;
    readnode = (wchar_t *)AllocReadRecord(readnode, CurrentNodeAddress);
    readnodebak = readnode;
    rpsave = record_preview;
}
else
{
    if(first_next == FIRST)
    {
        if(searchstring)
        {
            (char *)readnode += (unsigned)((char *)compareaddress - (char *)nodestruct);
            comparevalue = Compare(searchstring, readnode, comparelen, CompareKind);
        }
        else
            comparevalue = 0;

        if(!comparevalue)
        {
            ReturnValue = readnodebak;
            LastSearchedAddress[searchlevel] = CurrentNodeAddress;
            break;
        }
        else
        {
            if(Go(RIGHT))
            {
                readnode = readnodebak;
                delete readnode;
                readnode = (wchar_t *)AllocReadRecord(readnode, CurrentNodeAddress);
                readnodebak = readnode;
                rpsave = record_preview;
            }
            else
            {
                PopAddress = Pop(searchlevel);

                if(!PopAddress)
                    break;

                Go(PopAddress);
                readnode = readnodebak;
                delete[] readnode;
                readnode = (wchar_t *)AllocReadRecord(readnode, CurrentNodeAddress);
                readnodebak = readnode;
                rpsave = record_preview;
                rpsave.LeftAddress = 0;
            }
        }
    }
}
```

```
    }
    }
    else
    {
        first_next = FIRST;

        if(Go(RIGHT))
        {
            readnode = readnodebak;
            delete[] readnode;
            readnode = (wchar_t *)AllocReadRecord(readnode, CurrentNodeAddress);
            readnodebak = readnode;
            rpsave = record_preview;
        }
        else
        {
            PopAddress = Pop(searchlevel);

            if(!PopAddress)
                break;

            Go(PopAddress);
            readnode = readnodebak;
            delete[] readnode;
            readnode = (wchar_t *)AllocReadRecord(readnode, CurrentNodeAddress);
            readnodebak = readnode;
            rpsave = record_preview;
            rpsave.LeftAddress = 0;
        }
    }
}

if(readnode)
{
    readnode = readnodebak;
    delete[] readnode;
}

if(!ReturnValue)
    CurrentNodeAddress = CurrentNodeAddressbak;

return ReturnValue;
}
//-----
int Fbtree::Push(int address, int searchlevel)
{
    int ReturnValue = 1;

    StackPosition[searchlevel]++;
```

```
StackBak = new int[StackPosition[searchlevel] + 1];
if(!StackBak)
    ReturnValue = 0;
else
{
    for(register i = 0; i < StackPosition[searchlevel] - 1; i++)
        StackBak[i] = Stack[searchlevel][i];

    delete[] Stack[searchlevel];
    Stack[searchlevel] = StackBak;

    StackBak[StackPosition[searchlevel] - 1] = address;
}

return ReturnValue;
```

```
}
//-----
```

```
int Fbtree::Pop(int searchlevel)
{
    int ReturnValue = 0;
    if(StackPosition[searchlevel])
        ReturnValue = Stack[searchlevel][--StackPosition[searchlevel]];

    StackBak = new int[StackPosition[searchlevel] + 1];
    if(!StackBak)
        ReturnValue = 0;
    else
    {
        for(register i = 0; i < StackPosition[searchlevel]; i++)
            StackBak[i] = Stack[searchlevel][i];

        delete[] Stack[searchlevel];
        Stack[searchlevel] = StackBak;
    }

    return ReturnValue;
}
//-----
```

```
char Fbtree::Go(int where)
{
    char ReturnValue = 0;
    int sw = where < 41 ? (int)where : ADDRESS;

    if(Header.FirstNodeAddress && File->Handle > 0)
    {
        File->Seek(CurrentNodeAddress, soFromBeginning);
        File->Read(&record_preview, sizeof(RecordPreview));

        switch(sw)
        {
```

```
case LEFT:
    if(record_preview.LeftAddress)
    {
        ReturnValue = 1;
        CurrentNodeAddress = record_preview.LeftAddress;
    }
    break;

case RIGHT:
    if(record_preview.RightAddress)
    {
        ReturnValue = 1;
        CurrentNodeAddress = record_preview.RightAddress;
    }
    break;

case SUB:
    if(record_preview.SubNodeAddress)
    {
        ReturnValue = 1;
        CurrentNodeAddress = record_preview.SubNodeAddress;
        CurrentFileLevel++;
    }
    break;

case PREVIOUS:
    if(record_preview.PreviousNodeAddress)
    {
        ReturnValue = 1;
        CurrentNodeAddress = record_preview.PreviousNodeAddress;
    }
    break;

case MOTHER:
    if(record_preview.MotherNodeAddress)
    {
        ReturnValue = 1;
        CurrentNodeAddress = record_preview.MotherNodeAddress;
        CurrentFileLevel--;
    }
    break;

case TOP:
    while(record_preview.MotherNodeAddress)
    {
        ReturnValue = 1;
        Go(MOTHER);
    }

    Go(SUBTOP);
    CurrentFileLevel = 1;
    break;
```

```
    case SUBTOP:
        while(record_preview.PreviousNodeAddress)
        {
            ReturnValue = 1;
            Go(PREVIOUS);
        }
        break;

    case ADDRESS:
        if(where)
        {
            CurrentNodeAddress = where;

            if(IndexCounter)
            {
                int counter = 1;

                while(Go(MOTHER))
                    counter++;

                CurrentNodeAddress = where;
                CurrentFileLevel = counter;
            }

            ReturnValue = 1;
        }
        break;
    }
}
```

```
return ReturnValue;
```

```
//-----
char Fbtree::DeleteNode(void)
```

```
{
    RecordPreview rpsave;
    int savenodeaddress = CurrentNodeAddress;
    int othernodeaddress = 0;
    char ReturnValue = 0;
```

```
    if(Header.FirstNodeAddress && File->Handle > 0)
```

```
    {
        ReturnValue = PREVIOUS;
        OpenIndexFiles();

        File->Seek(CurrentNodeAddress, soFromBeginning);
        File->Read(&rpsave, sizeof(RecordPreview));

        void *buffer = AllocReadRecord(buffer, CurrentNodeAddress);
        RemoveAddressIndex(CurrentNodeAddress);
        delete[] buffer;
```

```
if (Go (PREVIOUS))
{
    File->Seek(CurrentNodeAddress, soFromBeginning);
    File->Read(&record_preview, sizeof(RecordPreview));

    if(!rpsave.LeftAddress || !rpsave.RightAddress)
    {
        if(!rpsave.LeftAddress)
        {
            if(record_preview.LeftAddress == savenodeaddress)
                record_preview.LeftAddress = rpsave.RightAddress;
            else
                record_preview.RightAddress = rpsave.RightAddress;

            File->Seek(CurrentNodeAddress, soFromBeginning);
            File->Write(&record_preview, sizeof(RecordPreview));

            if(rpsave.RightAddress)
                othernodeaddress = rpsave.RightAddress;
        }
        else
        {
            if(record_preview.LeftAddress == savenodeaddress)
                record_preview.LeftAddress = rpsave.LeftAddress;
            else
                record_preview.RightAddress = rpsave.LeftAddress;

            File->Seek(CurrentNodeAddress, soFromBeginning);
            File->Write(&record_preview, sizeof(RecordPreview));

            if(rpsave.LeftAddress)
                othernodeaddress = rpsave.LeftAddress;
        }

        if(othernodeaddress)
        {
            File->Seek(othernodeaddress, soFromBeginning);
            File->Read(&record_preview, sizeof(RecordPreview));
            record_preview.PreviousNodeAddress = rpsave.PreviousNodeAddress;
            File->Seek(othernodeaddress, soFromBeginning);
            File->Write(&record_preview, sizeof(RecordPreview));
        }
    }
    else
    {
        if(record_preview.LeftAddress == savenodeaddress)
            record_preview.LeftAddress = rpsave.LeftAddress;
        else
            record_preview.RightAddress = rpsave.LeftAddress;

        File->Seek(CurrentNodeAddress, soFromBeginning);
        File->Write(&record_preview, sizeof(RecordPreview));
    }
}
```

```
File->Seek(rpsave.LeftAddress, soFromBeginning);
File->Read(&record_preview, sizeof(RecordPreview));
record_preview.PreviousNodeAddress = rpsave.PreviousNodeAddress;
File->Seek(rpsave.LeftAddress, soFromBeginning);
File->Write(&record_preview, sizeof(RecordPreview));

CurrentNodeAddress = rpsave.LeftAddress;
while (Go (RIGHT));
File->Seek(CurrentNodeAddress, soFromBeginning);
File->Read(&record_preview, sizeof(RecordPreview));

record_preview.RightAddress = rpsave.RightAddress;
File->Seek(CurrentNodeAddress, soFromBeginning);
File->Write(&record_preview, sizeof(RecordPreview));

savenodeaddress = CurrentNodeAddress;

File->Seek(rpsave.RightAddress, soFromBeginning);
File->Read(&record_preview, sizeof(RecordPreview));
record_preview.PreviousNodeAddress = savenodeaddress;
File->Seek(rpsave.RightAddress, soFromBeginning);
File->Write(&record_preview, sizeof(RecordPreview));
}

CurrentNodeAddress = rpsave.PreviousNodeAddress;
}
else
{
if(rpsave.LeftAddress || rpsave.RightAddress)
{
if(!rpsave.LeftAddress || !rpsave.RightAddress)
{
if(!rpsave.LeftAddress)
{
Go (RIGHT);
ReturnValue = RIGHT;
}
else
{
Go (LEFT);
ReturnValue = LEFT;
}

File->Seek(CurrentNodeAddress, soFromBeginning);
File->Read(&record_preview, sizeof(RecordPreview));
record_preview.PreviousNodeAddress = 0;
record_preview.MotherNodeAddress = rpsave.MotherNodeAddress;
File->Seek(CurrentNodeAddress, soFromBeginning);
File->Write(&record_preview, sizeof(RecordPreview));

savenodeaddress = CurrentNodeAddress;

if (Go (MOTHER))
```

```
    {
        File->Seek(CurrentNodeAddress, soFromBeginning);
        File->Read(&record_preview, sizeof(RecordPreview));
        record_preview.SubNodeAddress = savenodeaddress;
        File->Seek(CurrentNodeAddress, soFromBeginning);
        File->Write(&record_preview, sizeof(RecordPreview));
    }
    else
    {
        Header.FirstNodeAddress = savenodeaddress;
        WriteHeader();
    }

    CurrentNodeAddress = savenodeaddress;
}
else
{
    if(Go(MOTHER))
    {
        File->Seek(CurrentNodeAddress, soFromBeginning);
        File->Read(&record_preview, sizeof(RecordPreview));
        record_preview.SubNodeAddress = rpsave.LeftAddress;
        File->Seek(CurrentNodeAddress, soFromBeginning);
        File->Write(&record_preview, sizeof(RecordPreview));
    }
    else
    {
        Header.FirstNodeAddress = rpsave.LeftAddress;
        WriteHeader();
    }

    File->Seek(rpsave.LeftAddress, soFromBeginning);
    File->Read(&record_preview, sizeof(RecordPreview));
    record_preview.PreviousNodeAddress = rpsave.PreviousNodeAddress;
    record_preview.MotherNodeAddress = rpsave.MotherNodeAddress;
    File->Seek(rpsave.LeftAddress, soFromBeginning);
    File->Write(&record_preview, sizeof(RecordPreview));

    CurrentNodeAddress = rpsave.LeftAddress;
    while(Go(RIGHT));
    File->Seek(CurrentNodeAddress, soFromBeginning);
    File->Read(&record_preview, sizeof(RecordPreview));

    record_preview.RightAddress = rpsave.RightAddress;
    File->Seek(CurrentNodeAddress, soFromBeginning);
    File->Write(&record_preview, sizeof(RecordPreview));

    savenodeaddress = CurrentNodeAddress;

    File->Seek(rpsave.RightAddress, soFromBeginning);
    File->Read(&record_preview, sizeof(RecordPreview));
    record_preview.PreviousNodeAddress = savenodeaddress;
    File->Seek(rpsave.RightAddress, soFromBeginning);
```

```
        File->Write(&record_preview, sizeof(RecordPreview));

        CurrentNodeAddress = rpsave.LeftAddress;
    }
}
else
{
    if(Go(MOTHER))
    {
        ReturnValue = MOTHER;
        File->Seek(CurrentNodeAddress, soFromBeginning);
        File->Read(&record_preview, sizeof(RecordPreview));
        record_preview.SubNodeAddress = 0;
        File->Seek(CurrentNodeAddress, soFromBeginning);
        File->Write(&record_preview, sizeof(RecordPreview));
    }
    else
    {
        ReturnValue = NULL;
        Header.FirstNodeAddress = 0;
        WriteHeader();
    }
}
}

CloseIndexFiles();
}

return ReturnValue;
}
//-----

void Fbtree::ReplaceNode(void *nodestruct, int nodestructsize)
{
    RecordPreview rpsave;
    long savenodeaddress;
    char deletevalue;

    if(Header.FirstNodeAddress && File->Handle > 0)
    {
        File->Seek(CurrentNodeAddress, soFromBeginning);
        File->Read(&rpsave, sizeof(RecordPreview));

        deletevalue = DeleteNode();
        if(deletevalue != MOTHER)
        {
            Go(SUBTOP);
            AddNode(nodestruct, nodestructsize, (char *)nodestruct + rpsave.KeyStartAddress, rpsave.KeyLen, rpsave.CompareKind);
        }
        else
            AddSubNode(nodestruct, nodestructsize, (char *)nodestruct + rpsave.KeyStartAddress, rpsave.KeyLen, rpsave.CompareKind);

        File->Seek(CurrentNodeAddress, soFromBeginning);
    }
}
```

```
File->Read(&record_preview, sizeof(RecordPreview));
record_preview.SubNodeAddress = rpsave.SubNodeAddress;
File->Seek(CurrentNodeAddress, soFromBeginning);
File->Write(&record_preview, sizeof(RecordPreview));

if(rpsave.SubNodeAddress)
{
    long counter = 0;
    void *result;

    savenodeaddress = CurrentNodeAddress;
    Go(SUB);
    do
    {
        if(!counter)
        {
            result = FreeSearch(MAXFBTREELEVEL, NULL, NULL, NULL, NULL);
            counter++;
        }
        else
            result = FreeSearch(MAXFBTREELEVEL, NULL, NULL, NULL, NULL, NEXT);

        if(result)
        {
            File->Seek(CurrentNodeAddress, soFromBeginning);
            File->Read(&record_preview, sizeof(RecordPreview));
            record_preview.MotherNodeAddress = savenodeaddress;
            File->Seek(CurrentNodeAddress, soFromBeginning);
            File->Write(&record_preview, sizeof(RecordPreview));
        }
    }while(result);

    Go(savenodeaddress);
}

if(deletevalue == MOTHER || (rpsave.MotherNodeAddress && (deletevalue == LEFT || deletevalue == RIGHT)))
{
    Go(SUBTOP);

    File->Seek(rpsave.MotherNodeAddress, soFromBeginning);
    File->Read(&record_preview, sizeof(RecordPreview));
    record_preview.SubNodeAddress = CurrentNodeAddress;
    File->Seek(rpsave.MotherNodeAddress, soFromBeginning);
    File->Write(&record_preview, sizeof(RecordPreview));
}

}

//-----

int Fbtree::MoveSubUp(void)
{
    //////////////////////////////////////
    //NOTICE:
```

```
//When the sub node is became move up, it loses
//its left and right node addresses.
//If this occurred, ReturnValue sets to 1, otherwise sets to 0;
```

```
//If current node has no sub node, it will be deleted;
```

```
////////////////////////////////////////////////////////////////////////////////////////////////////////////////////////////////
```

```
int ReturnValue = 0;
RecordPreview subrpsave = {NULL};
long savenodeaddress = CurrentNodeAddress;
wchar_t *readnode = NULL;
```

```
if(Go(SUB))
{
    File->Seek(CurrentNodeAddress, soFromBeginning);
    File->Read(&subrpsave, sizeof(RecordPreview));
    readnode = (wchar_t *)AllocReadRecord(readnode, CurrentNodeAddress);
}
}
```

```
Go(savenodeaddress);
```

```
DeleteNode();
```

```
if(subrpsave.MotherNodeAddress)
{
```

```
    Go(SUBTOP);
    AddNode(readnode, subrpsave.RecordLen, readnode + subrpsave.KeyStartAddress, subrpsave.KeyLen, subrpsave.CompareKind);
```

```
    File->Seek(CurrentNodeAddress, soFromBeginning);
    File->Read(&record_preview, sizeof(RecordPreview));
```

```
    record_preview.SubNodeAddress = subrpsave.SubNodeAddress;
    File->Seek(CurrentNodeAddress, soFromBeginning);
    File->Write(&record_preview, sizeof(RecordPreview));
```

```
    savenodeaddress = CurrentNodeAddress;
    if(Go(SUB))
```

```
    {
        File->Seek(CurrentNodeAddress, soFromBeginning);
        File->Read(&record_preview, sizeof(RecordPreview));
        record_preview.MotherNodeAddress = savenodeaddress;
        File->Seek(CurrentNodeAddress, soFromBeginning);
        File->Write(&record_preview, sizeof(RecordPreview));
    }
}
```

```
if(readnode)
    delete readnode;
```

```
Go(CurrentNodeAddress);
```

```
return ReturnValue;
```

```
}
//-----
```

```
char Fbtree::Optimize(void)
{
    char optimizefilename[128] = "OPTIMIZE.DAT";
    char ReturnValue = 0;

    bool del = _DeleteFile(optimizefilename, UseExecutionPath);

    if(del == true && File->Handle > 0)
    {
        OptimizeLevel = 0;
        CloseIndexFiles(true);

        Fbtree *opt_result = new Fbtree(optimizefilename, YES, CaseSensitive, CompareFunction, fbtree_index, UseExecutionPath, false);

        if(opt_result)
        {
            opt_result->OptimizeActive = YES;

            opt_result->OpenIndexFiles();

            Go(TOP);

            if(OptProccess(opt_result))
            {
                FbtreeHeader oldheader = Header;

                File->Size = sizeof(Header);
                File->Seek(sizeof(Header), soFromBeginning);
                opt_result->File->Seek(sizeof(Header), soFromBeginning);

                File->CopyFrom(opt_result->File, opt_result->File->Size - sizeof(Header));

                File->Seek(0, soFromBeginning);
                opt_result->File->Seek(0, soFromBeginning);

                memmove(&Header, &opt_result->Header, (int)(&Header.UserActive[0] - &Header.Header[0]));

                StrCopy(Header.Security1, oldheader.Security1);
                StrCopy(Header.Security2, oldheader.Security2);
                StrCopy(Header.Provider, oldheader.Provider);
                Header.Version = oldheader.Version;

                WriteHeader();
                CurrentNodeAddress = Header.FirstNodeAddress;
                ReturnValue = 1;
            }

            opt_result->CloseIndexFiles(true);
            delete opt_result;

            _DeleteFile(optimizefilename, UseExecutionPath);
        }
    }
}
```

```
        GetNextNewNodeAddress();

        if(OpenAllIndexes)
            OpenIndexFiles();
    }

    if(ProgressBar)
        ProgressBar->Position = ProgressBar->Min;

    return ReturnValue;
}
//-----
char Fbtree::OptProcess(Fbtree *opt_result)
{
    int i;
    char ReturnValue = 0;
    int address_handle;
    int record_counter = 0, address;
    char opt_filename[256];
    wchar_t *readnode = NULL;

    OptimizeLevel++;

    if(UseExecutionPath)
        sprintf(opt_filename, "%s\\address.%d", ExecutionPath, OptimizeLevel);
    else
        sprintf(opt_filename, "address.%d", OptimizeLevel);

    TFileStream *AddressFile = new TFileStream(opt_filename, fmCreate);

    if(AddressFile->Handle > 0)
    {
        ReturnValue = 1;

        if(FreeSearch(MAXFBTREELEVEL, NULL, NULL, NULL, NULL))
        {
            AddressFile->Write(&CurrentNodeAddress, sizeof(long));
            record_counter++;

            while(FreeSearch(MAXFBTREELEVEL, NULL, NULL, NULL, NULL, NEXT))
            {
                AddressFile->Write(&CurrentNodeAddress, sizeof(long));
                record_counter++;
            }
        }

        if(ProgressBar && OptimizeLevel == 1)
        {
            ProgressBar->Min = 0;
        }
    }
}
```

```

    ProgressBar->Max = record_counter;
    ProgressBar->Position = 0;
}

if(record_counter > 2)
{
    int random1 = 0, random2 = 0;
    int address1, address2;
    unsigned randomblock1, randomblock2, maxblock;

    randomize();
    maxblock = unsigned(record_counter / 32000);
    for(i = 0; i < record_counter; i++)
    {
        randomblock1 = random(maxblock + 1);
        randomblock2 = random(maxblock + 1);

        while(!random1)
            random2 = random1 = randomblock1 == maxblock ? random((unsigned)(record_counter % 32000)) : random(32000);

        while(random1 == random2 || !random2)
            random2 = randomblock2 == maxblock ? random((unsigned)(record_counter % 32000)) : random(32000);

        AddressFile->Seek((randomblock1 * 32000 + random1) * sizeof(long), soFromBeginning);
        AddressFile->Read(&address1, sizeof(long));
        AddressFile->Seek((randomblock2 * 32000 + random2) * sizeof(long), soFromBeginning);
        AddressFile->Read(&address2, sizeof(long));

        AddressFile->Seek((randomblock1 * 32000 + random1) * sizeof(long), soFromBeginning);
        AddressFile->Write(&address2, sizeof(long));
        AddressFile->Seek((randomblock2 * 32000 + random2) * sizeof(long), soFromBeginning);
        AddressFile->Write(&address1, sizeof(long));

        random1 = random2 = 0;
    }
}

AddressFile->Seek(0, soFromBeginning);

for(i = 0; i < record_counter; i++)
{
    if(ProgressBar && OptimizeLevel == 1)
    {
        ProgressBar->Position = record_counter;

        if(ProgressBar->Max > 100)
        {
            if(!(record_counter%(ProgressBar->Max / 100)))
                Application->ProcessMessages();
        }
        else
            Application->ProcessMessages();
    }
}

```

```
    AddressFile->Read(&address, sizeof(long));
    Go(address);

    readnode = (wchar_t *)AllocReadRecord(readnode, CurrentNodeAddress);

    if(!i)
        opt_result->AddSubNode((void *)readnode, record_preview.RecordLen, (char *)readnode + record_preview.KeyStartAddress,
record_preview.KeyLen, record_preview.CompareKind);
    else
    {
        opt_result->Go(SUBTOP);
        opt_result->AddNode((void *)readnode, record_preview.RecordLen, (char *)readnode + record_preview.KeyStartAddress,
record_preview.KeyLen, record_preview.CompareKind);
    }

    if(readnode)
        delete[] readnode;

    if(record_preview.SubNodeAddress)
    {
        Go(SUB);

        ReturnValue = OptProcess(opt_result);
        opt_result->Go(MOTHER);
        Go(MOTHER);
    }
    delete AddressFile;

    _DeleteFile(opt_filename, false/*UseExecutionPath*/);
}

OptimizeLevel--;

return ReturnValue;
}
//-----

int Fbtree::PreIndex(int index_number)
{
    int ReturnValue = index_number;

    for(register i = 0; i < index_number; i++)
        if(!strcmp(fbtree_index[index_number].Filename, fbtree_index[i].Filename) && Index[i])
        {
            ReturnValue = i;
            break;
        }

    return ReturnValue;
}
//-----
```

```

void Fbtree::OpenIndexFiles(void)
{
    register i;

    if(!OpenIndexFlag)
        for(i = 0; i < IndexCounter; i++)
            if((OpenAllIndexes || OptimizeActive == YES || CurrentFileLevel == fbtree_index[i].Level || (CurrentFileLevel >=
fbtree_index[i].Level && fbtree_index[i].IncludeSubNodes)) && PreIndex(i) == i)
                {
                    if(OptimizeActive == YES)
                        _DeleteFile(fbtree_index[i].Filename, UseExecutionPath);

                    Index[i] = new Fbtree(fbtree_index[i].Filename, YES, CaseSensitive, fbtree_index[i].Comp, NULL, UseExecutionPath);
                }

    OpenIndexFlag++;
}
//-----

void Fbtree::CloseIndexFiles(bool ForceClose)
{
    register i;

    OpenIndexFlag--;

    if(!OpenIndexFlag || ForceClose)
        {
            for(i = IndexCounter - 1; i >= 0; i--)
                if(Index[i])
                    {
                        delete Index[i];
                        Index[i] = NULL;
                    }

            OpenIndexFlag = 0;
        }
}
//-----

void Fbtree::WriteIndex(void *nodestruct, unsigned delete_address)
{
    void *result;
    int PreIndex_number;

    for(register i = 0; i < IndexCounter; i++)
        if(CurrentFileLevel == fbtree_index[i].Level || (CurrentFileLevel >= fbtree_index[i].Level && fbtree_index[i].IncludeSubNodes))
            {
                wchar_t ch = 1;
                char addsub = 1;
                char *buffer = new char[fbtree_index[i].Len + 2];

                PreIndex_number = PreIndex(i);
            }
}

```

```
memmove(buffer, (char *)nodestruct + fbtree_index[i].StartKey, fbtree_index[i].Len);
buffer[fbtree_index[i].Len] = 0;

Index[PreIndex_number]->Go(TOP);

fbtree_currentindex_sign = fbtree_index[i].Sign;

result = Index[PreIndex_number]->BSearch(&ch);
if(!result)
    Index[PreIndex_number]->AddNode(&ch, sizeof(wchar_t), &ch, sizeof(wchar_t), fbtCHAR);
else
    if(Index[PreIndex_number]->Go(SUB))
    {
        result = Index[PreIndex_number]->BSearch(buffer);
        addsub = 0;
    }
    else
        result = NULL;

if(!result)
{
    if(addsub)
        Index[PreIndex_number]->AddSubNode(buffer, wcslen((wchar_t *)buffer) * sizeof(wchar_t) + 2, buffer,
fbtree_index[i].Len, fbtree_index[i].CompareKind);
    else
        Index[PreIndex_number]->AddNode(buffer, wcslen((wchar_t *)buffer) * sizeof(wchar_t) + 2, buffer,
fbtree_index[i].Len, fbtree_index[i].CompareKind);

    Index[PreIndex_number]->AddSubNode(&CurrentNodeAddress, sizeof(int), &CurrentNodeAddress, sizeof(int), fbtLONG);
}
else
{
    if(Index[PreIndex_number]->Go(SUB))
    {
        result = NULL;

        if(delete_address)
            result = Index[PreIndex_number]->BSearch(&delete_address);

        if(result)
        {
            if(Index[PreIndex_number]->DeleteNode() == MOTHER)
                Index[PreIndex_number]->AddSubNode(&CurrentNodeAddress, sizeof(long), &CurrentNodeAddress, sizeof(long),
fbtLONG);

            else
                Index[PreIndex_number]->AddNode(&CurrentNodeAddress, sizeof(long), &CurrentNodeAddress, sizeof(long),
fbtLONG);

        }
        else
            Index[PreIndex_number]->AddNode(&CurrentNodeAddress, sizeof(long), &CurrentNodeAddress, sizeof(long),
fbtLONG);
    }
}
```

```
        else
            Index[PreIndex_number]->AddSubNode(&CurrentNodeAddress, sizeof(long), &CurrentNodeAddress, sizeof(long), fbtLONG);
    }

    delete[] buffer;
}

//-----

void Fbtree::RemoveAddressIndex(unsigned delete_address)
{
    void *result;
    int PreIndex_number;
    wchar_t ch = 0;

    for(register i = 0; i < IndexCounter; i++)
        if(CurrentFileLevel == fbtree_index[i].Level || (CurrentFileLevel >= fbtree_index[i].Level && fbtree_index[i].IncludeSubNodes))
        {
            PreIndex_number = PreIndex(i);

            Index[PreIndex_number]->Go(TOP);

            fbtree_currentindex_sign = fbtree_index[i].Sign;

            result = Index[PreIndex_number]->BSearch(&ch);

            if(!result)
                Index[PreIndex_number]->AddNode(&ch, sizeof(wchar_t), &ch, sizeof(wchar_t), fbtCHAR);

            Index[PreIndex_number]->AddSubNode(&delete_address, sizeof(long), &delete_address, sizeof(long), fbtLONG);
        }
}

//-----

unsigned Fbtree::GoIndexAddress(char *filename, void *searchbuffer, int occurrence_number)
{
    unsigned ReturnValue = 0;
    wchar_t ch;

    OpenIndexFiles();
    for(register i = 0; i < IndexCounter; i++)
        if(!strcmp(fbtree_index[i].Filename, filename))
        {
            ch = 1;
            Fbtree *index_file = Index[i];

            if(index_file)
            {
                index_file->Go(TOP);
                if(index_file->BSearch(&ch))
                    if(index_file->Go(SUB))
                    {
                        if(index_file->BSearch(searchbuffer))

```

```
    {
        if(index_file->Go(SUB))
        {
            void *result;
            unsigned long find_address = 0;

            result = index_file->FreeSearch(MAXFBTREELEVEL, NULL, NULL, NULL, NULL);

            for(register j = 1; j < occurrence_number; j++)
                result = index_file->FreeSearch(MAXFBTREELEVEL, NULL, NULL, NULL, NULL, NEXT);

            if(result)
            {
                index_file->GetCurrentNode(&find_address);

                ReturnValue = find_address;

                index_file->Go(TOP);
                ch = 0;

                if(index_file->BSearch(&ch))
                    if(index_file->Go(SUB))
                        if(index_file->BSearch(&find_address))
                            ReturnValue = find_address = DELETED_INDEX;

                if(ReturnValue)
                    Go(find_address);
            }
        }
    }
}

CloseIndexFiles();
return ReturnValue;
}
//-----

void Fbtree::SetHeaderProviderVersion(char *Provider, float Version)
{
    StrLCopy(Header.Provider, Provider, 49);
    Header.Version = Version;
    WriteHeader();
}
//-----

bool Fbtree::CheckProviderVersion(char *Provider, float Version)
{
    bool ReturnValue = true;

    if(StrComp(Header.Provider, Provider))
        ReturnValue = false;
}
```

```
if(Header.Version != Version)
    ReturnValue = false;
```

```
return ReturnValue;
```

```
}
```

```
//-----
```

```
AnsiString __fastcall Fbtree::GetExecutionPath(void)
```

```
{
    return ExtractFileDir(ParamStr(0));
```

```
}
```

```
//-----
```

```
#ifndef H_FBTREE
#define H_FBTREE

#include "ComCtrls.hpp"

#define MAXFBTREELEVEL 100
#define MAXFBTREEINDEX 10

#define fbtSTRING 1
#define fbtINTEGER 2
#define fbtLONG 3
#define fbtFLOAT 4
#define fbtDOUBLE 5
#define fbtDATE 6
#define fbtCHAR 7
#define fbtFREECOMPARE 8

#define YES true
#define NO false

#define DELETED_INDEX 4294967295L

#define LEFT 1
#define RIGHT 2
#define SUB 3
#define MOTHER 4
#define TOP 5
#define SUBTOP 6
#define ADDRESS 7
#define CENTER 8
#define TOPLEFT 9
#define TOPRIGHT 10
#define SEARCH 11
#define NEXT 12
#define PREVIOUS 13
#define ALL 14
#define FIRST 15
#define CURRENT 16
#define LAST 17

struct FbtreeIndex
{
    char *Filename;
    int Level;
    int StartKey;
    int Len;
    int (*Comp)(WideString s1, WideString s2, unsigned len);
    char CompareKind;
    char Sign;
    bool IncludeSubNodes;
};
```

```

struct RecordPreview
{
    long LeftAddress, RightAddress;
    long SubNodeAddress, MotherNodeAddress;
    long PreviousNodeAddress;
    unsigned RecordLen, KeyStartAddress, KeyLen;
    char CompareKind;
};

```

```

struct FbtreeHeader
{
    char Header[17];
    char EndOfFile;
    char Security1[11];
    char Security2[11];
    unsigned long FirstNodeAddress;
    char Provider[50];
    float Version;
    char Reserved[30];
    char UserActive[512];
};

```

```

class Fbtree
{
    int Access;
    unsigned Mode;
    long NewNodeAddress, PreviousNodeAddress;
    long LastSearchedAddress[MAXFBTREELEVEL + 1];
    char PreviousPath;
    bool CaseSensitive;
    bool OpenAllIndexes;
    int *Stack[MAXFBTREELEVEL + 1], *StackBak;
    int StackPosition[MAXFBTREELEVEL + 1];
    int OptimizeLevel;
    bool OptimizeActive;
    int OpenIndexFlag;
    int CurrentFileLevel;
    char FbtreeFilename[128];
    int (*CompareFunction)(WideString s1, WideString s2, unsigned len);

    FbtreeIndex *fbtree_index;
    Fbtree *Index[MAXFBTREEINDEX];
    int IndexCounter;

    void GetNextNewNodeAddress(void);
    void WriteNewRecord(void *nodestruct);
    void ReadRecord(void *nodestruct, long nodeaddress = -1);
    void *AllocReadRecord(void *nodestruct, long nodeaddress);
    int Push(int address, int searchlevel);
    int Pop(int searchlevel);
};

```

```
char OptProcess(Fbtree *opt_result);
int Compare(void *comp1, void *comp2, unsigned size, char comparekind);
void WriteIndex(void *nodestruct, unsigned delete_address = NULL);
void RemoveAddressIndex(unsigned delete_address);
int PreIndex(int index_number);
bool UseExecutionPath;

public:
    TFileStream *File;
    bool Found;
    int CurrentNodeAddress;

    FbtreeHeader Header;
    RecordPreview record_preview;
    TProgressBar *ProgressBar;

    void WriteHeader(char *source = NULL, int start = 0, int size = 1);
    void ReadHeader(char *dest = NULL, int start = 0, int size = 1);
    char AddNode(void *nodestruct, int nodestructsize, void *startnodekey, int keysize, char comparekind = fbtSTRING, int nodeaddress =
-1);
    char AddSubNode(void *nodestruct, int nodestructsize, void *stratnodekey, int keysize, char comparekind = fbtSTRING, int nodeaddress =
-1);
    void *BSearch(void *searchstring, int startaddress = -1);
    void *FreeSearch(int searchlevel, void *searchstring, void *nodestruct, void *compareaddress, unsigned comparelen, char firstornext =
FIRST, char comparekind = fbtSTRING);
    char GetCurrentNode(void *nodestruct);
    char Go(int where);
    void OpenIndexFiles(void);
    void CloseIndexFiles(bool ForceClose = false);
    char DeleteNode(void);
    void ReplaceNode(void *nodestruct, int nodestructsize);
    int MoveSubUp(void);
    char Optimize(void);
    unsigned GoIndexAddress(char *filename, void *searchbuffer, int occurrence_number = 1);
    void *AllocGetCurrentNode(void *nodestruct);
    void SetHeaderProviderVersion(char *Provider, float Version);
    bool CheckProviderVersion(char *Provider, float Version);
    AnsiString __fastcall GetExecutionPath(void);

    Fbtree(char *filename, bool change_header = YES, bool casesens = NO, int (*comp)(WideString s1, WideString s2, unsigned len) = NULL,
FbtreeIndex *f_index = NULL, bool use_execpath = YES, bool OpenIndexes = YES);
    ~Fbtree(void);
};

#endif
```